

NATURANCE

Nature for insurance,
insurance for nature

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**Deliverable 4.3: Recommendations for integrating
NbS in insurance schemes based on the synthesized
and improved catastrophe models and other methods
and empirical evidence base (M39) (VU)**

WP4

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Deliverable Title	Recommendations for integrating NbS in insurance schemes based on the synthesized and improved catastrophe models and other methods and empirical evidence base
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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a set of recommendations to mainstream investment in Nature-based Solutions (NBS) for climate risk reduction and how insurance may contribute to the scaling up of NbS. These recommendations are a result of the improved methods developed during the previous deliverables of the Naturance project (D4.1, D4.2) and the Innovation Labs from WP2 of NATURANCE. We combined the output of a newly developed flood risk model and a Discrete Choice Experiment for monetizing NBS co-benefits to conduct a societal Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) applied to different NBS options in the Netherlands. Additionally, we perform an analysis on how these NBS policies can impact insurance premiums and insurance demand. Moreover, we explore how insurance may contribute to investment in NbS or stimulate the implementation of NBS by their policyholders. Together, these components demonstrate the economic feasibility of NBS, and the role insurance can play in stimulating NbS.

The deliverable first synthesizes the progress on developing shared metrics and standards to evaluate NBS performance. These metrics provide a foundation for assessing effectiveness, transparency and comparability across projects. Standardization is critical to ensure that insurers and policymakers can quantify the contribution of NBS to risk reduction or other societal issues. Building on this, an overview of financial instruments that can enable NBS investment is presented. These instruments were identified through a literature review and discussed with experts in an Innovation Lab (WP2). The Lab discussion highlighted the importance of blended finance structures and stronger policy alignment to attract private capital for NBS. Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) were ranked as the best instrument to mainstream investment in NBS among participants. The labs emphasized that while grants and public funding remain essential to initiate projects, private participation is key for scaling NBS implementation and ensuring long-term sustainability. This is complemented by a discussion regarding Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) policy, which was discussed in another WP2 Innovation Lab, by focusing on several case studies.

Then, the focus of the deliverable shifts to the case study of the European Floods of 2021, introduced in Deliverable 4.2, which highlighted the need for an improved flood risk management strategy.. We present results of a CBA that compares different NBS scenarios to assess the economic feasibility of NBS for flood risk reduction over time, accounting for risk reduction benefits and societal co-benefits based on the improved methods and metrics designed in WP4. The results highlight how neglecting co-benefits in the CBA can reduce the viability of NBS, particularly when these require a large number of hectares of land. New alternatives that do not require purchasing the land or where a combination of risk reduction NBS and farming activities can be conducted on the same land, could be viable solutions to solve this issue and increase acceptance from the community. This is in line with the concerns which were raised during the WP2 Innovation Lab sessions, where local stakeholders highlighted land use as the main obstacle, which was later confirmed in the Discrete Choice Experiment results.

An integration of the effects of NBS on flood risk reduction in the Dynamic Integrated Flood Insurance (DIFI) model shows that, as a result of the effectiveness of NBS in reducing expected annual damage as shown in the flood risk model, the percentage of uninsured risk (coverage gap)

would drop by almost 50%. Moreover, our results demonstrate that investment in NBS by insurance can be a viable business case under the condition of a public or public-private flood insurance arrangement. The last section looks into an alternative way for insurance to incentivize NBS adoption by their policyholders through premium discounts and shows that insurance-based incentives are an effective way of promoting green roof adoption. Overall, this deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of the benefits and costs of NBS, in order to inform policymakers and private sector investors about how they perform in different scenarios. The results of our improved methods and metrics in WP4 underscore the effectiveness of NBS from a societal perspective and the need for collaboration between public and private partners to mainstream investment in NBS that reduce climate risk.

The key recommendations for the scaling up of investment in NBS for the public and private sector are:

- Employ shared metrics and standards to allow for comparability of the effectiveness and desirability of NBS. The metrics proposed in this report allow an assessment on a broad welfare perspective.
- Enable collaborations between the public sector and the private sector in order to collect, analyse, and share relevant data, incorporating relevant indicators and metrics. Alternatively, the public sector can collect open-access data.
- Integrate NBS in spatially detailed catastrophe models that can provide actionable insights into risk reduction, premiums and insurability.
- Assessing flood-risk reduction of NBS requires basin-scale simulations to capture upstream and downstream interactions.
- Stimulating private finance for NBS is dependent on the type of insurance system. In the case of a public-private insurance system, there can be a business case for insurers to invest in NBS for risk reduction.
- Even in the case of a purely public or private system, the assessment of risk-reduction from NBS is still relevant to identify the beneficiaries.
- Complement the risk-reduction estimates with a co-benefits assessment. Monetizing co-benefits in a societal cost-benefit analysis is key to illustrate the economic viability of NBS.
- Account for land-use change as a key component of financial feasibility of NBS. Its financial and social impact should not be neglected by policymakers. Innovative solutions that combine agricultural practices and NBS could increase viability and social acceptance.
- Promote alternative insurance financing mechanisms, such as premium-based incentives for insurance policyholders to adopt NBS.
- Consider private-public partnerships, grants, and insurance schemes as they play central roles in de-risking and legitimising investments, but could be complemented by payment for ecosystem services, territorial branding, biodiversity credits, or community financing to secure local buy-in and diversified revenue streams.
- Implement public policies, such as the Biodiversity Net Gain in the UK, as a potential way for enabling NBS. The insurance sector plays a key role in helping developers and environmental consultants mitigate potential liabilities arising from Biodiversity Net Gain projects.

1 Introduction

The increasing frequency and severity of climate-related hazards highlights the need for investing in climate change mitigation and adaptation (IPCC, 2021). The number of climate-related events is projected to increase from 400 in 2015 to more than 550 by 2030 (The International Disaster Database, 2022). The economic losses associated with such events - floods, heatwaves, wildfires - are estimated at USD 150-200 billion annually, compared to USD 50 billion in 1980 (Munich Re, 2022). To this end, nature-based solutions (NBS) could become useful and effective in limiting climate risk. NBS are defined as “solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social, and economic benefits and help build resilience” (European Commission, 2019). NBS may mitigate natural hazards by for example mediating peak water flow and nuisances, or through the maintenance of stable physical, chemical, and biological conditions.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide recommendations on integrating NbS in insurance schemes based on the synthesized and improved catastrophe models and other methods and empirical evidence base developed in WP4. In particular, we explore the role of integrating different methods to estimate risk reduction, co-benefits assessment and impact on insurance in mainstreaming investment in NBS for climate risk reduction. NBS can be low-cost climate risk-reduction alternatives, which can particularly be cost-effective in areas with lower exposure to climate hazards. As of today, 85% of global investments in NBS is provided by the public sector (IUCN, 2021). Nevertheless, NBS may still be attractive for private sector investors. From an insurance perspective, the resulting risk reduction from NBS can lead to premium reduction (as long as premiums are risk-based), which as a result would imply higher affordability and a larger client base. Additionally, areas that are currently deemed as uninsurable due to the risk being too high, could become insurable again if the risk reduces due to NBS. Lastly, the size and volume of claims would also be reduced. This report focuses on how conducting a comprehensive assessment of the full range of benefits and costs of NBS, including co-benefits, is key to enable an uptake of NBS initiatives. Throughout this deliverable, the main challenges identified by different stakeholders and how we addressed these through quantitative modelling and metric assessment will be discussed. While insurers have a clear stake in managing climate risk and can benefit from lower risk, the path for integrating NBS into the business model involves several challenges, from data availability to coordination with public sector stakeholders. During the conversation of stakeholders in the WP2 Innovation Labs, instruments that combined public and private sector actors were seen as the most feasible since public financing is needed in the earlier stages but private capital can facilitate long term success and upscaling.

To overcome these challenges, this deliverable employs the models developed at previous stages in the NATURANCE project (Deliverable 4.1. And 4.2.) and the input from stakeholders in the WP2 Innovation Lab to apply them in a real policy context. Building on the review and meta-analysis conducted as part of Deliverable 4.1., which synthesized global evidence on NBS effectiveness, we identified a lack of standards and metrics for assessing NBS performance, a lack of consideration for co-benefits, NBS not being included in catastrophe modelling, and how NBS benefits are highly context-specific. Hence, the next steps focused on targeting these challenges. To address the lack

of standardization, we have included a section in this deliverable where we discuss recent efforts in standardization of metrics to assess the performance of NBS. Subsequently we assess some of these key metrics by building on Deliverable 4.2 in which we produced a new object-based hydrological model that is able to quantify the impact of NBS and a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) distributed as a stated preference survey in the case study area with the intention of monetizing co-benefits of NBS. This addresses several of the challenges identified by Deliverable 4.1 and NATURANCE stakeholders from practice by including NBS in risk reduction analysis, accounting for co-benefits and producing policy recommendations by performing a local analysis. These methods benefited greatly from the discussions with local stakeholders and NATURANCE knowledge networks from both insurance and the public sector in the Innovation Labs (WP2), as they highlighted key challenges that ultimately improved the DCE design. As a result, this deliverable integrates the results into an applied Cost-benefit Analysis (CBA) together with the further improved Dynamic Integrated Flood Insurance (DIFI) model to show how different NBS policies can impact risk-reduction, societal welfare and the insurance market. The use of the DIFI model in this case study also supports the work conducted in WP3 on the potential contribution of the insurance industry to investing in NBS.

In this deliverable, we are also interested in assessing how these economic benefits can actually translate to investment and policymaking in practice. There are several ways in which insurance can support the uptake of NBS. For instance, insurers can directly invest in NBS projects or in a Public-Private Partnership with the government and other partners of the private sector which also have an incentive to participate (e.g. banks). Additionally, insurance can also play a key role by providing incentives for customers to adopt small-scale NBS through a premium discount. Nevertheless, there are certain challenges that should be addressed. Whereas some types of NBS may be attractive to insurers, such as those applicable by individual policyholders, the “common good” nature of benefits may be an obstacle for insurers to be the sole investor. This is particularly true in competitive private insurance markets, where policyholders can easily switch insurance contracts. Blended finance structures, potentially led by public authorities, may be needed to upscale larger NBS strategies, such as those needed to reduce riverine flood risk. In this deliverable, we explore the premium discount strategy through a case study in the Netherlands, showing that insurance-based incentives can indeed lead to an uptake in green roof adoption. To sum up, the methods and metrics developed for this report demonstrates that NBS can be key in future climate risk management strategies. It also shows how the insurance sector can be involved in promoting NBS either through direct investment or by incentivizing adoption through premium discounts.

The deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of metrics and standards for assessing NBS performance. Section 3 shows the outcome of a literature review and conversation with stakeholders in an Innovation Lab, where the key financing instruments for NBS are discussed in detail and ranked by experts. Section 4 focuses on the outcomes of an Innovation Lab on the Biodiversity Net Gain policy in the UK. Section 5 introduces the quantification of metrics using our improved methods that are input for the societal CBA and insurance modelling. Section 6 explores the role of insurance in promoting green roof uptake through premium discounts. Section 7 concludes with our recommendations, including those for integrating NBS in insurance schemes.

2 Overview of Metrics and Standards

Shared metrics provide evidence that can be assessed, compared, and used to track performance, quality, and change. Metrics shall show, in a consistent and transparent way, whether a nature-based insurance and investment solution is material to risk, delivers the intended outcomes, and represents good value across places and over time. In this document, shared metrics refer to a common set of qualitative and quantitative indicators, definitions, and evidence-gathering rules that support underwriting, investment, and public decision-making through an auditable and proportionate framework for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL).

How do other frameworks and standards treat the shared metrics?

The **ISO family of standards on climate change adaptation** provides a coherent and practical framework to help organizations, communities, and governments prepare for, respond to, and manage the impacts of a changing climate. The series is built around ISO 14090, the world's first International Standard on climate adaptation¹, which establishes the core principles, requirements, and guidelines for climate change adaptation. It is complemented by related standards that provide detailed guidance for specific dimensions of adaptation, such as vulnerability and risk assessment, local adaptation planning, and performance-based mechanisms for financing adaptation.

- **ISO 14090:2019** *Adaptation to climate change: Principles, requirements and guidelines*² defines indicators as measurable variables, either quantitative or qualitative, used to monitor and evaluate the progress and effectiveness of climate change adaptation actions. The term *metrics* is not explicitly used but indicators are treated as functionally equivalent to shared metrics, serving to measure performance, outcomes, and adaptive capacity over time. Organisations are required to establish a structured framework for *Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning* (MEL), including a formal plan that specifies objectives, responsibilities, data sources, and review procedures. Periodic monitoring should be conducive for learning and lessons learned that improve future planning and decision-making and adjusted when new information becomes available. Indicators are expected to capture both short-term progress and long-term outcomes, making it possible to compare between baselines. The standard distinguishes between **process** indicators (e.g., inputs and resources), **outcome** indicators (evidence of improved adaptive capacity), and **impact** indicators (observable changes in risk or vulnerability).
- **ISO 14091:2021** *Adaptation to climate change: Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment*³ defines indicators as quantitative, qualitative, or binary variables that can be measured or described in reference to specific criteria. The indicators describe drivers of climate risk such as *hazard, exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity*, and can include both direct measures and proxies, for instance pest incidence as a proxy for crop damage. Indicators serve the same purpose as metrics (which are not defined) by measures that can

be combined into composite risk indices. The standard promotes a transparent, participatory, and iterative approach to climate risk assessment that supports continuous learning and improvement. It requires clear documentation of objectives, data sources, and uncertainties, along with quality assurance and independent review. Indicators may be quantitative, semi-quantitative, or qualitative and are used to evaluate climate-related hazards, the exposure of people and assets, their sensitivity, and the capacity to adapt. ISO 14091 lays the groundwork for monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL), and stresses that adaptation decisions are evidence-based, transparent, and comparable across contexts.

- **ISO/TS 14092:2020** *Adaptation to climate change: Requirements and guidance on adaptation planning for local governments and communities*⁴ complements ISO 14090 and 14091 by focusing specifically on the practical application of adaptation planning at the local level. It introduces operational requirements for integrating MEL directly into municipal decision-making and resource management processes. The standard emphasizes the practicality of indicators, requiring them to be measurable with available local data, comparable across jurisdictions, and easy to communicate to non-specialist stakeholders. It also places stronger emphasis on participatory and transparent governance, recommending that adaptation performance data and lessons learned be publicly reported and used to refine local strategies.
- **ISO 14093:2022** *Adaptation to climate change: Local mechanisms for financing adaptation through performance-based climate resilience grants*⁵ builds on the earlier ISO 14090–92 standards and focuses on mechanisms for channeling climate finance to subnational authorities through **performance-based climate resilience grants (PBCRG)**. It uses the term performance metrics (as “*set of indicators against which subnational authorities are assessed on an annual basis*”). Indicators and metrics are defined as measurable variables that serve to assess both minimum conditions (such as governance, participation, transparency, and financial management) and performance (effectiveness of climate adaptation). Indicators shall be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-related (SMART) but can evolve over time, becoming more demanding as local capacities improve. The standard introduces a robust performance-based monitoring system which links the flow of climate finance to measurable performance outcomes. It requires a transparent scoring and verification process, consistency in annual evaluations, and accountability and learning. The MEL framework embraces continuous improvement by annual progress reviews which also includes review or update of indicators based on new data or policy shifts. The standard differentiates between minimum condition indicators (ensuring compliance with governance and fiduciary standards) and performance indicators (assessing the quality and outcomes of adaptation investments). Examples include the use of climate risk assessments in planning, integration of adaptation into budgeting, procurement transparency, and inclusion of vulnerable groups in decision-making. Adaptation-specific

indicators must represent at least 50% of all performance metrics. Each indicator contributes to assessing progress toward resilience objectives and influences future financial allocations, creating a direct link between performance and funding. Although ISO 14093:2022 was developed to guide national and local governments in managing performance-based climate resilience grants, the principles are also relevant to *private and blended investments*. The standard provides an auditable approach for linking financial flows to verified adaptation outcomes through measurable indicators and transparent MEL systems, the aspects of which can be readily adapted to nature-based insurance and investment solutions. This means that ISO 14093 can serve as a robust reference model for developing shared, performance-based metrics that connect capital allocation with demonstrable improvements in climate resilience, ecological integrity, and social value.

The ISO 32210 and related standards are part of a broader ISO initiative to embed **sustainability and climate resilience within financial and environmental management**. Sustainable finance focuses on mobilizing financial resources and market structures to support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to address climate change. They promote the integration of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations across all types of financing. ISO 32210 provides the overarching principles and guidance for sustainable finance, while [related standards](#) expand on these foundations. ISO 32220, *Sustainable finance: Basic concepts and key initiatives*, was published in 2021, and ISO 32211, *Principles and guidelines for the development and implementation of sustainable finance products and services*, is currently under development. Together, they offer a coherent framework that enables financial institutions, investors, and other stakeholders to align capital flows with sustainability objectives, strengthen transparency, and create enduring value.

- **ISO 32210:2022** *Sustainable finance: Principles and guidance*⁶ has created a comprehensive framework for sustainable finance, including how financial institutions and investors integrate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations into decision-making and performance management. The standard defines indicators and metrics¹ as measurable, evidence-based variables used to evaluate material sustainability impacts across an organization's operations and value chain. Both quantitative and qualitative metrics are recognized, provided they are transparent, verifiable, and supported by a clear evidence base and source of verification. The standard requires that organizations embed monitoring, measurement, and evaluation within their overall sustainability management framework. Indicators should be specific to sustainability objectives, measurable (quantitatively or qualitatively), achievable in practice, relevant to the organizational context, and time-bound.

¹ Metric is defined as a measurement method and measurement scale that can demonstrate contribution to a key performance indicator.

The standard recommends using only a limited **set of core indicators**, balancing robustness with data availability and reporting capacity. Measurement processes should align with the company's strategy, stakeholder expectations, and recognized international or regulatory standards. Indicators are used to track progress toward strategic sustainability goals, identify performance gaps, and inform both internal management decisions and external reporting. Examples include *process-based indicators* (e.g., governance and risk management quality), *performance indicators* (e.g., emissions intensity, social inclusion metrics, or economic resilience measures), and *outcome indicators* that reflect real-world impact.

In addition to the above standards and building a bridge between climate adaptation and sustainable finance, ISO 14097 provides a framework and guiding principles for assessing and reporting investment and financing activities related to climate change. It enables financial institutions and investors to evaluate and disclose how their actions contribute to climate mitigation and adaptation.

- **ISO 14097** *Greenhouse gas management and related activities: Framework including principles and requirements for assessing and reporting investments and financing activities related to climate change* introduces a framework that extends the ISO environmental management standards into the financial domain, guiding how financial organisations assess and report the climate impact of their investments and lending. It defines key terms such as climate action, output, outcome, and impact, framing them as measurable elements of a cause-effect chain that links financial decisions to climate goals. Indicators are not explicitly labeled as “metrics,” but they appear throughout as quantitative or qualitative measures used to monitor changes in greenhouse gas emissions, resilience, and adaptive capacity. The standard requires financiers (investors or lenders) to set clear, measurable targets, monitor progress, and document causal linkages between actions, outputs, outcomes, and impacts, following principles of transparency, accuracy, and additionality. The monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) framework is structured around a continuous process of defining expected results, collecting evidence, and assessing performance. Financiers must develop a monitoring plan that identifies indicators, data sources, frequency, and responsibilities, and report annually on results and any changes in assumptions or external conditions. This structure enables both ex-ante planning and ex-post evaluation of the effectiveness of climate-related financial actions.

Other ISO standards are relevant for designing the shared metrics, as they provide a methodological, financial, and environmental framework that ensures indicators are measurable, verifiable, and aligned with international best practices.

- **ISO 17298:2025** *Biodiversity: Considering biodiversity in the strategy and operations of organizations, Requirements and guidelines* marks the first international guidance dedicated

exclusively to biodiversity for organisations⁸. It sets to guide organisations in understanding and managing how their activities affect and depend on nature. It offers a structured framework for integrating biodiversity into strategic decision-making and operations, helping all types of organizations (from businesses to public entities) to assess impacts and dependencies, prioritize actions, and set measurable objectives aligned with global initiatives such as the *Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*. The standard also supports unlocking nature-positive finance, enhancing transparency in nature-related performance, and building resilience within supply chains and value chains.

- **ISO 37123:2019 *Sustainable cities and communities: Indicators for resilient cities***⁹ provides a comprehensive framework for measuring and reporting the resilience of cities. Building on the ISO 37100 family of standards for sustainable communities, it defines indicators as standardized quantitative or qualitative measures used to assess the adaptive capacity of cities and the continuity of essential services. The standard establishes a consistent and verifiable framework for collecting and reporting data. It requires cities to consider their specific exposure, vulnerabilities, and institutional capacities when using indicators. The indicators are organized thematically across key domains such as economy, governance, health, housing, environment, and infrastructure, and they are aligned with international frameworks including the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction SFDRR 2015-2030 and the SDGs. Examples include the percentage of insured properties in hazard-prone areas, the frequency of extreme weather events, the share of city land under ecosystem restoration, and the proportion of public services with continuity plans.
- The **ISO 14030 *Environmental performance evaluation: Green debt instruments*** series stands for a comprehensive framework for the environmental performance evaluation of green debt instruments. It provides standardized guidance for the issuance, management, and verification of financial products such as green bonds and green loans, so that these instruments contribute to environmental objectives, including climate change, adaptation and nature protection. Developed under ISO Technical Committee 207 on environmental management, the series includes several standards already published or under development: *ISO/CD 14030-1* defines the principles, requirements, and guidance for designating bonds and other debt instruments as green. It covers the processes for project selection, management of proceeds, and the definition, measurement, and reporting of environmental impacts. *ISO/CD 14030-2* applies similar guidance to green loans, focusing on eligibility and exclusion criteria as well as procedures to identify and manage material environmental and social risks. *ISO/CD 14030-3* specifies the taxonomy and verification requirements that ensure consistency and credibility in assessing the environmental integrity of both bonds and loans. *ISO/CD 14030-4* complements the previous parts by outlining principles and guidance for the verification of green debt instruments beyond bonds, promoting transparency and assurance in environmental claims¹⁰.

- **ISO 14008:2019** *Monetary valuation of environmental impacts and related environmental aspects* provides a standardized framework for assigning economic values to environmental impacts, helping organizations quantify how their activities affect natural systems and ecosystem services. The standard defines principles, requirements, and guidelines for conducting monetary valuation in a transparent, consistent, and scientifically robust manner. The standard can be applied to a wide range of contexts, including environmental management, life cycle assessment, policy evaluation, and financial decision-making. It guides users in identifying relevant environmental impacts (such as air pollution, water use, land degradation, or biodiversity loss), selecting appropriate valuation methods (for example, market prices, avoided costs, or willingness-to-pay approaches), and expressing the results in monetary terms.

Proposal for the shared metrics

Shared metrics **break down the guiding principles** into evidence that can be assessed, compared, and used to track performance, quality, and change. In this document, we use the terms metrics and indicators in a way consistent with the relevant ISO standards and the IPCC Assessment Reports. A *metric* is defined as a consistent measurement of a characteristic of an object, system, or activity that can be used to assess the condition or performance of a solution (both project/NBS intervention and product/financial instrument). An indicator, in turn, is an *interpreted metric*, that is a policy-relevant signal derived from one or more metrics to show progress toward a defined objective, target, or condition. Using the term **shared metrics**, we place emphasis on both the metrics (i.e. the measurement methods, units, and scale) and the derived indicators, to underscore that how an indicator is measured is as important as what it represents.

We use the distinction between condition and performance to capture two complementary dimensions: *Condition* metrics assess whether the enabling conditions for implementation of similar solutions exist (e.g. governance, financing, ecosystem integrity). *Performance* metrics assess how effectively the solutions operate or deliver on intended outcomes and impacts (e.g. risk reduction, investment return, biodiversity benefit). In practice, most metrics in this framework will relate to performance, while maintaining a consistent reference to underlying conditions that influence replicability and scalability.

The common characteristic of all shared metrics is that they are both scientifically sound and policy meaningful. This means they should be specific, measurable, relevant, and time-related (in line with existing standards such as ISO 14093:2022) and, in addition, proportionate to the scope and scale of the solution, as well as sensitive to the changes induced by that solution. Metrics are:

- *Specific* when they target a clearly defined area for improvement or performance assessment.
- *Measurable* when they are based on quantifiable or observable data, supported by documented methods, data sources, and assumptions that can be replicated and verified by an independent third party.

- *Relevant* when they capture aspects that are material for decision-making, investment, or policy evaluation, and directly reflect the objectives of the solution being assessed.
- *Time-related* and *sensitive to change* when they are linked to the timing of results or outcomes and capable of detecting meaningful variations in performance or conditions over time.
- *Proportionate* when the complexity and precision of measurement are aligned with the scale and purpose of the assessment, practical and not overburden the assessment.

Purpose and use context of the metrics: Each solution [(comprising a nature-based intervention, the project, and a financial instrument, the product)] is assessed independently. This means that every solution represents its own unit of analysis and reporting, and the purpose of the assessment is to determine whether it is sound, credible, and appropriate for adoption or investment. For insurers, investors, and policymakers, it may be relevant to compare multiple solutions to select among them or to construct a portfolio of complementary solutions. This CWA focusses on the individual solutions and is not designed to provide a full portfolio-level analysis. The metrics serve primarily ex-ante assessment, supporting decision-making before implementation or investment, and periodic ex-post assessment as a part of revisions to track performance and relevance over time. The revisions can lead to discontinuing a solution, suspending underwriting, or withdrawing invested capital if conditions or performance indicators no longer meet agreed levels.

Consistent conceptual framework: The metrics should be embedded in a clear conceptual framework [/, such as a *pathway to impact* or a *theory of change*,] that explains how a solution generates the intended impacts. This framework should describe the logical progression from inputs, for example financial investments, to outputs, such as the implementation of the nature-based project, then to outcomes, such as reduced exposure or avoided losses, and finally to impacts, such as broader and sustained improvements in resilience. For nature-based insurance and investment solutions, this pathway usually links financial inputs with activities that restore or protect nature, which in turn lead to risk reduction or resilience outcomes and ultimately to wider socio-economic, or corporate environmental benefits. A well-defined causal framework makes it possible to select and interpret metrics in specific cases. It clarifies what is being measured, why it matters, and how change is expected to occur. It also helps to demonstrate that different categories of metrics (economic, financial, environmental, social, and governance) are consistent with one another and together capture the full chain of value creation [/, from resource mobilization to risk reduction and societal resilience].

Categories of metrics and trade-offs between them: In this CWA, the metrics are organised into categories that reflect guiding principles and established practices. These categories include economic, financial, environmental, social, and governance dimensions. The categories are designed to be complementary rather than overlapping, although in some cases the attribution of specific metrics may not be unique to a single category. In many cases, trade-offs between categories are inevitable. For example, a solution may achieve a high financial return while delivering only modest ecological restoration, or vice versa. Such trade-offs should be explicitly acknowledged and transparently reflected in the purpose and design of the solution, to illuminate the value judgements and priorities that shape it.

Alignment with established frameworks: The metrics should be aligned with established international and European frameworks (such as EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance), standards (such as ISO 14093:2022 on adaptation finance), and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This alignment increases the comparability, interoperability, and policy relevance of the metrics, and reduces the reporting fatigue across broader regulatory, financial, and sustainability reporting systems.

Economic soundness explains whether a solution “makes sense” within the broader social welfare system. It is not limited to the perspective of investors or insurers but considers the value of the solution to *society as a whole*. In other words, it assesses whether the solution is worth implementing once all site-specific and wider private and public benefits are taken into account.

The key measure of economic soundness is the extent to which the solution reduces risk, expressed in physical terms, such as reductions in peak flow levels in the case of floods, or in economic terms, such as reductions in annual expected damage and loss or in event-based damages and losses. The assessment should consider not only direct and site-specific benefits but also wider or induced effects, recognising that risks and their consequences often propagate across sectors and geographic boundaries. The cost of implementation and maintenance should also be considered.

Another important measure is the cumulative weight of co-benefits that are not directly linked to risk mitigation but result from restored or protected ecosystem services. These may include improved water quality, biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, recreational value, or cultural benefits. Although such co-benefits may be more difficult to quantify, they significantly enhance the overall societal value of the solution and should be acknowledged explicitly.

In practice, direct and verifiable benefits will often take precedence in the evaluation, but the recognition and qualitative appraisal of wider and induced benefits are essential for a comprehensive understanding of the solution’s contribution to resilience and social welfare.

Table 2.1 Categories and examples of metrics for economic soundness of a solutions

Subcategory	Metric / Indicator	Description / Measurement Method
Risk reduction	Change in annual expected damage and loss (absolute and %)	Difference in expected annual damages or losses between the baseline and project scenarios. Derived from hazard, exposure, and vulnerability models.
	Change in event-based loss or damage	Avoided damage for defined hazard events (e.g., 1-in-100-year flood) compared with the baseline condition.
	Reduction in physical risk parameters	Physical improvements such as peak flow reduction, temperature moderation, erosion control, or flood extent reduction.
	Beneficiaries protected or exposure reduced	Number of people, households, or assets benefiting from the intervention, or the total exposure reduced within the project area.

Co-benefits	Ecosystem service enhancement index	Improvements in key ecosystem services (e.g., water quality, carbon sequestration, biodiversity habitat, recreational value). Include biophysical or proxy indicators.
	Social and cultural benefit score	Non-market benefits such as improved wellbeing, community engagement, or cultural and recreational value associated with restored ecosystems.
	Cross-sectoral impact description	Qualitative or semi-quantitative assessment of induced positive effects in other sectors or regions (e.g., improved water retention benefiting agriculture or energy).
Economic materiality	Benefit–cost ratio (BCR)	Present value of avoided damages and co-benefits to the total cost of implementation and maintenance.
	Net Present Value (NPV)	Sum of the present value of avoided damages and co-benefits minus the sum of the present value of the total cost of implementation and maintenance
	Loss avoided per euro invested	Measure of efficiency, showing how much loss is prevented for each euro invested.
	Indicative premium or capital requirement effect	Potential change in insurance premiums or capital costs due to the verified reduction in risk.
	Payback period	Time required for cumulative avoided losses and co-benefits to equal investment costs.
Robustness and credibility	Documentation of models, data, and assumptions	Transparency and reproducibility of methods and data sources used for baseline and project scenarios
	Uncertainty range or sensitivity analysis	Confidence interval or range of variability in key metrics under different plausible scenarios
	Third-party verification	Independent review and validation of risk and benefit assessments
	Compliance with relevant standards and frameworks	Alignment with applicable standards for adaptation and sustainable finance

Financial viability provides a detailed overview of the financial structure of a solution, including how it is funded, operated, and sustained over time. It sets out a comprehensive breakdown of the costs associated with implementing the project, in this case the nature-based intervention itself, and explains how these costs are recovered or repaid. It also identifies additional costs that may arise

throughout the solution’s lifetime, such as operation, maintenance, monitoring, or end-of-life and decommissioning activities, together with the contingency management of financial and operational risks.

Financial viability distinguishes who pays and how, while economic soundness considers whether the solution is worth it socially. Unlike economic soundness, which focuses on the overall value of the solution to society, financial viability examines how costs and liabilities are distributed among the actors involved. It does so within the framework of a viable lifecycle business case that shows how each participant contributes to financing, bears risks, and benefits from the returns or avoided losses generated by the solution.

Some categories of benefits, such as the value of ecosystem services, are also relevant for financial viability, and **may appear as redundant**. In reality, these benefits are included again, not for their contribution to social welfare, but to account for the portion of their value already internalised in the financial model, the revenue stream, or the repayment and investment decisions.

Table 2.2 Categories and examples of metrics for financial viability of a solutions

Dimension	Metric / Indicator	Description / Measurement Method
Cost structure and efficiency	Capital and operating cost breakdown	Total capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX), including monitoring, maintenance, and, where relevant, end-of-life or decommissioning costs
	Cost per unit of risk reduced	Total cost of implementation and operation divided by the quantified risk reduction (for example, avoided loss per year or per exposed asset)
	Lifecycle cost coverage ratio	Secured or projected revenues and repayments to total lifecycle costs, indicating whether the business case is financially sustainable
Funding and revenue structure	Confirmed funding sources and repayment pathways	Committed funding streams, revenue sources, or repayment mechanisms (for example, public grants, insurance savings, loans, or blended finance)
	Leverage of private and public capital	Proportion of private and public funding and the degree of financial leverage achieved through co-financing arrangements
	Greenium or avoided-loss savings captured	Reductions in financing costs or realised savings resulting from improved risk profile or sustainability value
Financial resilience and risk management	Sensitivity and scenario analysis	Financial performance changes under plausible variations in key assumptions such as hazard intensity, maintenance costs, or discount rate

	Contingency and reserve provisions	Adequacy of contingency funds, guarantees, or reserve mechanisms for unexpected costs or performance shortfalls
	Alignment with insurance and underwriting logic	Mapping of expected risk reduction to underwriting, coverage terms, and pricing, including treatment of basis risk in parametric solutions
Revenue and benefit distribution	Benefit allocation map (who pays and who benefits) Co-benefit monetization or value capture ratio	Distribution of costs, benefits, and liabilities among actors and beneficiaries, including public and private stakeholders Proportion of measurable co-benefits (for example, ecosystem services or avoided losses) that are incorporated into the revenue or repayment model
Robustness and credibility	Transparency of financial assumptions and data Independent financial or technical review Compliance with relevant standards and taxonomies	Cost estimates, discount rates, and financial assumptions clearly documented and verifiable Business case has been reviewed or audited by qualified external parties Alignment with applicable standards for adaptation and sustainable finance

Evidence of **environmental integrity** should demonstrate that each solution contributes to positive ecological gains (such as improved habitat quality, increased biodiversity, enhanced ecosystem connectivity) within a larger landscape or catchment context and avoids harm.

The requirement on the projects to deliver **net nature-positive outcomes** means that, over the lifetime of a project, the overall condition of nature and ecosystems is improved rather than degraded, once all positive and negative impacts are taken into account. Ecosystems affected by the project should be in better condition or provide higher levels of ecosystem services than before the intervention. In practice, this means that any negative environmental impacts resulting from the project’s implementation, operation, or maintenance are avoided, minimised, or restored. In the context of this CWA, this principle means that financial and risk-reduction benefits are achieved in synergy with ecological integrity.

Table 2.3 Categories and examples of metrics for environmental integrity of a solutions

Dimension	Metric / Indicator	Description / Measurement Method
Nature-positive outcome	Net change in habitat condition or area	Comparison of pre- and post-project habitat condition (quality, extent, or functionality) using recognised metrics such as habitat condition

		indices, species richness, or ecosystem integrity scores
	Biodiversity net gain (%)	Percentage increase in biodiversity or ecological value relative to the baseline, calculated through standardised biodiversity accounting methods (e.g., habitat hectares)
	Ecosystem service enhancement index	Changes in ecosystem service provision (e.g., water retention, carbon storage, soil fertility, pollination) based on modelling or biophysical assessments
Avoidance of harm	Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)	Project meets DNSH criteria under the EU Taxonomy; no significant harm occurs to other environmental objectives
	Residual impact and offset ratio	Remaining negative impacts and documents measures for restoration or offsetting to ensure a net positive outcome
Ecological design and contextual fit	Alignment with local ecological context	Design choices (species selection, hydrological design, landscape configuration) reflect local ecological, geomorphological, and climatic conditions
	Integration with landscape or catchment strategy	Project fits within broader ecological processes or regional restoration and conservation plans
Monitoring, maintenance, and adaptive management	Ecological monitoring plan and frequency	Ongoing monitoring programme is in place, with clearly defined indicators, data sources, and reporting intervals
	Adaptive management plan	Existence of a structured plan to revise practices or targets when monitoring results diverge from expectations
	Stewardship and governance arrangements	Long-term management and financing responsibilities, including community or institutional roles in stewardship
	Transparency and disclosure of results	Monitoring results and revisions are reported transparently and accessible to relevant stakeholders
	Compliance with relevant standards and taxonomies	Alignment with applicable standards for adaptation and sustainable finance

Social value and ethical practice metrics substantiate the guiding principle of fairness and inclusion, through status indicators that show whether the minimum conditions for equitable and ethical

implementation have been met. These metrics complement the previous categories by verifying that the societal outcomes of a solution are fairly distributed and that the solution does not reinforce pre-existing structural inequalities. They demonstrate to what extent benefits and burdens are shared appropriately, that local and traditional knowledge is respected, and that all stakeholders have a genuine opportunity to participate in shaping and benefiting from the solution. These metrics for social value are presented in Table 2.4. These are closely linked to the Deliverable 3.2, where equitable and sustainable business models were presented.

Table 2.4 Categories and examples of metrics for social value & ethical practice of a solutions

Dimension	Metric / Indicator	Description / Measurement Method
Stakeholder engagement and participation	SH engagement plan and implementation	Existence of a documented and time-bound engagement plan, with identified SH, consultation methods, and how feedback is used in design and implementation
	Inclusiveness and representation index	Diversity and representativeness of SH engaged, including gender, age, vulnerable groups, and local communities
	Community ownership or participation level	Extent to which communities are involved in decision-making, management, or monitoring (for example, through local committees or stewardship agreements)
Equity and benefit distribution	Benefit-sharing arrangements	Existence and fairness of benefit-sharing or compensation mechanisms that ensure equitable access to benefits and distribution of costs and risks
	Affordability and access provisions	Existence of provisions to ensure affordability or access for disadvantaged or vulnerable groups
	Distributional equity assessment	Extent to which benefits and burdens are distributed fairly and do not reinforce structural inequalities
Respect for rights and cultural values	Integration of local and traditional knowledge	Recognition and integration of indigenous, local, or traditional knowledge into design and management
	Cultural heritage and land tenure rights	Solution respect land tenure rights and protect cultural heritage sites and practices
Transparency, accountability, and ethical governance	Transparency of methods and results	Assesses whether consultation outcomes, design changes, and performance reports are publicly available and communicated in accessible language

Social and ethical risk assessment	Potential social or ethical risks have been identified, assessed, and mitigated, including conflict potential or exclusion risks
Compliance with relevant standards and taxonomies	Alignment with applicable standards for adaptation and sustainable finance

Governance, data, and assurance metrics examine the processes through which solutions are designed, managed, and supported by evidence, rather than their performance outcomes. For that reason, they focus on the credibility, traceability, and consistency of results, assessing whether these processes are managed in a transparent, accountable, and verifiable manner throughout the entire life cycle of the solution. They complement the previous categories by evaluating how well a solution is monitored and verified, whether decisions are based on reliable information, and whether commitments made during design or investment stages are upheld during implementation and operation. This includes the clear specification of roles and responsibilities, the tracking and reporting of performance using recognised quality standards, and the existence of mechanisms for correction, learning, and independent assurance. In practical terms, governance, data, and assurance metrics form the institutional backbone of the overall framework, ensuring that the evidence supporting each solution is both trustworthy and enduring.

Table 2.5 Categories and examples of metrics for governance, data & assurance practice of NBS

Dimension	Metric / Indicator	Description / Measurement Method
Governance structure and accountability	Roles and responsibilities	Governance documents (contracts, mandates, or memoranda of understanding) clearly specify who is responsible for delivery, operation, maintenance, and corrective action
	Decision-making and oversight mechanisms	Existence of procedures for decision-making, approval, and oversight, including independent review or board-level supervision where relevant.
	Long-term management	Responsibilities for long-term stewardship and maintenance beyond the initial pilot period.
Policy and regulatory alignment	Alignment with policy and regulatory frameworks	Alignment with national and international adaptation, DRR, environmental, and financial regulations is explicitly documented
Data quality and management	Data quality assurance and documentation	Datasets meet defined quality criteria, including origin, version control, validation, and transparency of assumptions.
Monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV)	Existence of MRV plan	Monitoring, reporting, and verification schemes exists, with specified indicators, frequency, responsibilities, and data sources

	Independent review or third-party assurance	Key results are independently verified, audited, or reviewed at critical milestones
Correction, learning, and adaptive management	Corrective-action procedures Adaptive management framework	Existence of procedures that specify how underperformance is addressed and by whom. Mechanism for learning and iterative improvement, with adjustments based on monitoring outcomes.

These metrics are linked with the instruments presented in the next section. The metrics are not intended to be applied uniformly for all cases, as some may be more relevant than others for each specific case. For instance, insurance schemes depend on robust risk-reduction metrics (e.g. changes in expected annual damage), whereas instruments like payment for ecosystem services or biodiversity credits may emphasize the social performance and ecological metrics. In the following section, we delve into these financial instruments to mainstream investment in NBS.

3 Overview of financial instruments

The involvement of private sector capital alongside public funds is crucial to bridge the financing gap in climate adaptation (see Deliverable 3.1 for a detailed assessment). As of today, 84% of global funding for NBS comes from the public sector. However, the instruments introduced in this section can help to increase the investment from the private sector side. In this section, we will start providing the results of a review that summarizes the main instruments used globally before focusing on the outcomes of an Innovation Lab (WP2) led by KIT, where experts discussed the main challenges and enablers they identified for these financial instruments.

3.1 Financial instruments for NbS investments

In recent years, several instruments are being applied to mainstream investment in NBS for climate risk reduction. A recent literature review has identified over 60 different financial instruments that can help promote NbS (Bill-Weilandt et al., 2025). Out of this list, 59% were risk transfer instruments (nature-positive resilience insurance, etc.) and 24% were debt instruments, including green bonds, resilience bonds, debt-for nature swaps, etc. The majority of the entries to the global inventory of instruments came either from North America (23), Europe (13), Latin America (14) and East Asia & Pacific (14). The main instruments are presented in Sections 3.1.1 - 3.1.10, including their definition, relevance and real-world application with examples. These instruments are further discussed in Section 3.2, including the perspective of experts in the field.

A recent literature review identified that the most cited strategies to mainstream investment in NBS are knowledge sharing, fostering of innovative and alternative financing models and collaboration (Biasin et al., 2024). Insurers, banks, real estate firms and water utility companies were named as key stakeholders whose contributions are likely to be key to upscaling NBS. Another key recent development is the Sustainable Finance Inventory (McDonald et al., 2023), which consists of a total of 22 financing instruments for NBS². The tool, which focuses on pond development, allows users to select the most appropriate financing instrument, conditional on the scale of the project, financial complexity and role of the business. Some of the instruments identified here will be discussed in more detail in the next section, including public-private partnerships, grants, market-based instruments, impact investment and green bonds.

Table 3.1 Overview of financial instruments

Name	Type	Stakeholders needed
Public-private partnerships (PPPs)	Blended finance / contractual arrangements	Governments, development banks, private investors, insurers, utilities, project developers, communities

² PONDERFUL inventory: <https://www.ecologic.eu/19473>

Insurance schemes	Risk transfer / market-based	Insurers, reinsurers, governments (for subsidies/PPP), local communities, businesses, NGOs (for monitoring/restoration)
Green bonds	Market-based	Governments, municipalities, development banks, corporates, banks (underwriters), institutional investors
Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES)	Market-based / incentive scheme	Landowners, farmers, utilities, municipalities, businesses (beneficiaries), NGOs, regulators, financial intermediaries
Environmental Impact Bonds (EIBs)	Outcome-based / blended finance	Investors, utilities, local governments, outcome payers (e.g. philanthropies, agencies), evaluators, communities
Grants	Public finance	Governments, multilateral climate funds (GEF, GCF), donors, foundations, NGOs, local implementing partners
Biodiversity offsets	Regulatory compliance / market-based	Developers, regulators, mitigation banks, conservation NGOs, landowners, verification bodies
Impact funds (e.g. Natural Capital funds)	Market-based (private equity / debt impact investing)	Fund managers, DFIs, private investors, corporates, local project developers, NGOs
Biodiversity credits	Market-based (voluntary/regulated credits)	Project developers, crediting standards, buyers (corporates, investors), regulators, verification bodies, local communities
Swap schemes (land/yield swaps)	Community-based / compensation mechanism	Governments, communities, landholders, cooperatives, NGOs, local institutions
Resilience / Forest Resilience Bonds	Outcome-based / blended	Investors, utilities, insurers, governments, NGOs, project developers, evaluators
Disaster-risk funds (e.g. Barnier Fund)	Public finance (insurance-levy backed)	Governments, insurers, reinsurers, citizens (policyholders), local agencies implementing NbS

There are still however several barriers that limit private financing in NBS. The main barrier is the public nature of some of the goods provided by NBS that lack market valuation, lowering the incentives for the private sector to invest. As identified in a report by the European Investment Bank, another key barrier is that financial returns of NBS are often long-term and uncertain, with high transaction costs, technical complexity and a shortage of accurate data (EIB, 2023). Moreover, some of the instruments that are discussed in this section require considerable coordination efforts across public agencies and private sector investors. Lastly, insufficient awareness of NBS benefits (mainly co-benefits) contribute to the current reliance on traditional infrastructure (Raymond et al., 2017).

3.1.1 Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)

As defined by the World Bank (2025), PPPs entail “a long-term contract between a private party and a government entity, for providing a public asset or service, in which the private party bears significant risk and management responsibility and remuneration is linked to performance”. In this case, some of the benefits of NBS increase societal welfare. The non-market nature of these co-benefits hampers private investment, but could result in a good opportunity for PPPs. This arrangement is specially useful in financing large-scale NBS that require long-term maintenance (OECD, 2018).

When it comes to NBS, PPP can help mainstream investment in NBS by leveraging private sector expertise and investment for sustainable infrastructure. PPPs for NBS combine public sector goals with the private sector profit-seeking incentives by securing long-term financing and sharing risks effectively. A pioneering example is the Quintana Roo coral reef insurance in Mexico (Green Finance Institute, 2020). The PPP was established between the state government, hotel owners, The Nature Conservancy and private insurers. The Coastal Zone Management Trust collects levies from coastal businesses and uses them to purchase insurance for reef restoration after hurricanes.

Results of recent studies that involved key stakeholders seem to reinforce the idea that PPPs are among the preferred options both by insurers, local communities and the public sector (Linnerooth-Bayer et al., 2013). When presented with options, workshop participants agreed that government involvement through investment or compensation, while also supporting an agreed insurance premium discount for low-income vulnerable households that would have been unable to afford private insurance otherwise.

3.1.2 Insurance schemes

Insurance schemes can directly incentivize investment in NBS by recognizing ecosystems as assets that can reduce disaster risks. These insurance schemes transfer climate risk by reducing premiums after NBS interventions due to their impact on risk reduction. Similarly, insurers can also offer discounted premiums when policyholders (or communities) invest in NBS that reduce their individual climate risk. The application varies across countries, since there are multiple types and schemes in operation depending on the insurance market. The type of market can also pose one of the most significant challenges. For instance, the one-year contracts in competitive private insurance markets can discourage insurers to invest directly on NBS for a particular area, since the policyholders can switch to their competitors after one year (From Innovation Lab).

In the United States, the National Flood Insurance Program (NFIP) offers premium discounts for communities that preserve floodplains and wetlands, with the objective of incentivizing NBS adoption (FEMA, 2025). A pilot in Nicaragua allowed farmers to pay insurance premiums with conservation labor, in order to align agricultural risk reduction and ecosystem restoration (CGIAR, 2018).

3.1.3 Green bonds

Green bonds are defined as fixed-income instruments with the aim of financing projects that are beneficial for the environment and can serve to channel resources toward NBS for climate risk reduction (ICMA, 2021). Green bonds can either be issued by private firms, such as commercial banks, as well as by governments or international bodies. The North-Rhine Westphalia Green Bond in Germany allocated approximately €50 million in order to restore the Emscher river with the objective of enhancing flood resilience (NRW, 2019). In 2023, the Federal Ministry of Finance issued a Green Bond of €17.25 billion of which a 4% was allocated to NBS projects such as coastal protection and sustainable forestry (Federal Ministry of Finance, 2023). These cases illustrate how Green Bonds are a useful tool to mainstream investment in NBS. The green bond market is projected to grow to USD 620 billion by 2025 (Moody's, 2025).

3.1.4 Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES)

An alternative approach to promote NBS is to pay landholders or communities for managing ecosystems that deliver services to reduce climate risk or other co-benefits. The UN defines PES as “a tool through which a provider of ecosystem services receives payments for the management of ecosystems with the goal of continued or improved provision of services” (UNCCD, 2021). For instance, the beneficiaries (water utilities, municipalities, insurers, etc.) pay providers (farmers, landowners, communities) for defined ecosystem services such as flood mitigation. These can be done through tariffs, contributions, contracts or taxes. PES mechanisms align private financial incentives with public resilience objectives, by creating an incentive for conservation and restoration as part of the risk management strategy (Dextre et al., 2022).

A recent study found that 54% of these arrangements were supported by government investment, whereas 29% by private investment. Currently, this approach is mostly used for forests since 80% of the identified studies focused on this type of ecosystem (Sangha, 2024). However, such market-driven arrangements can lead to unequal distribution of benefits by focusing on net benefits provided by nature. The distribution of benefits is influenced by several factors such as the political, social and economic context, the voices included in the decision-making process and the payment mechanism employed (Thompson et al., 2023).

A concrete example of PES for NBS can be found in the Quito Water Fund. This PES channelled payments from municipalities and private companies into páramo and watershed conservation to protect Quito's water supply and reduce flood and drought hazards (Goldman-Benner et al., 2012; Kaufmann, 2014). In the United States, the Conservation Reserve Program pays farmers to improve flood control by retiring erosion-prone land (USDA, 2020).

3.1.5 Environmental Impact Bonds (EIB)

EIBs are financial models that focus on environmental challenges. Through them, public agencies work together with private capital and nonprofit organizations to fund cost-effective solutions. The public entity pays a return to investors only if the intervention meets or exceeds previously agreed-upon performance targets or outcomes (Trotta, 2024). In this case, the return on investment

depends on the outcome of the project. EIBs align financial returns and incentives climate risk reduction (Gustafsson-Wright et al., 2017).

In the United Kingdom, United Utilities raised a GBP 300 million sustainable bond in 2021. A part of the funds were used to restore peatlands and riverbanks, in order to improve water quality (Triodos, 2025). EIBs illustrate how outcome-based schemes can scale NBS under uncertainty. However, the limited pipeline of investor-ready projects holds green bonds back. Many of these projects are localised and long term, which means that it can be challenging to aggregate sufficient projects into a portfolio to back a multi-million benchmark bond, partly because early-stage financing is scarce for developing NBS projects to the point where they can absorb investments through a bond.

3.1.6 Grants

Grants can play an important role in mainstreaming investment for NBS. They provide necessary capital to support the early-stage development and implementation of NBS, particularly in scenarios where financial returns are uncertain or long-term. Grants are issued by governments or international organizations in order to start projects that would otherwise struggle to attract private capital due to uncertainty or lack of private incentives of non-market benefits. For instance, the Green Climate Fund (GCF) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF) have funded projects that enhance risk reduction (GCF, 2023; GEF, 2022). Despite the potential of grants for kick-starting projects, they are still limited by public budget constraints and private co-financing is likely necessary as support at later stages.

3.1.7 Biodiversity offsets

According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature, biodiversity offsets are conservation actions or outcomes designed to compensate for unavoidable environmental impacts on biodiversity that remain after all efforts to avoid, minimize or restore these impacts have been exhausted (IUCN, 2021). The aim of offsets is to achieve No Net Loss (NNL) and preferably a Net Gain (NG) of biodiversity when projects take place. The EU introduced a NNL policy framework that has boosted the development of offset schemes (European Commission, 2015).

Regulatory authorities set equivalence criteria (e.g. habitat type, ecological functionality) and monitor performance over time (Bull et al., 2013). Specialized entities restore and conserve habitats and then sell credits to developers. Offsets can be a component of a NBS strategy by providing conservation funding, restoring habitats, or creating new protected areas to enhance biodiversity (Brears, 2022). Offsets can finance NBS by directing private developer money into restoration of wetlands, floodplains, forests, or coastal ecosystems that provide both biodiversity and climate risk reduction benefits. For example, wetland restoration also enhances natural flood buffers, linking compensation mechanisms to resilience outcomes (Robertson, 2006; Maron et al., 2015). In Australia, state-level biodiversity offset policies often involve forest restoration or protection (Maron et al., 2015).

3.1.8 Impact funds

Generally, impact funds consist of “deploying funds into investments that generate a measurable and beneficial social or environmental impact alongside a financial return on investment” (UNPD, 2022). This is a way of increasing the private sector’s contribution to sustainable development. These investment funds still seek financial returns, while also focusing on environmental benefits. These benefits can be assessed using metrics such as ESG indicators.

For instance, ASN Impact has three primary impact funds involved in generating climate and nature-positive outcomes in Europe (EIB, 2023). The first is a market finance impact fund and the second involves renewable sources of energy. The third impact fund invests in positive biodiversity outcomes, which are mainly in four sectors: sustainable forestry, agroforestry, ecotourism and aquaculture in marine protected areas. Another example of impact funds is the Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) Fund, which is a partnership between Mirova and UNCCD, and mobilizes public and private capital into agriculture and forestry projects with risk-sharing mechanisms to attract private investors (UNCCD, 2020).

3.1.9 Crowdfunding/community financing

Community financing is an alternative that can gather small contributions from the public to fund NBS projects. The capital can be raised through local fundraising events or online platforms. Project organizers collect donations or investments from members of the community who benefit from the project or want to participate. It can be particularly effective in small-scale urban NBS projects, such as funding tree planting. Crowdfunding takes various forms – from pure donations to equity or debt models – enabling people to invest in NBS businesses or infrastructure with the prospect of returns. Ideally, this initial financing can help attract investors if the initial fundraising succeeds. Overall, community-based funding has emerged as a way to democratize NBS finance. An example is the RaiseGreen platform, which allows community investors to fund green infrastructure projects (Global Infrastructure Hub, 2024).

3.1.10 ESG

Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) investing can help to attract capital to nature-positive projects and NBS. As investors and regulators pay more attention to biodiversity and climate risks, companies may be incentivized to incorporate NBS into their ESG strategies. A notable case is the oil company Shell investing in a mangrove restoration project in Senegal, expecting to generate 1.7 million carbon credits while protecting coasts (SP Global, 2024).

3.1.11 Biodiversity credits

Biodiversity credits are market-based instruments that assign a tradable value to conservation outcomes (Alvaro-Quesada et al., 2014). A biodiversity credit represents a unit of positive biodiversity outcome that can be marketed (Wauchope et al. 2024). There is a similarity between biodiversity and carbon credits, however they focus on ecosystem services and biodiversity. They are considered an emerging vehicle for pro-environmental financing as these units intend to finance

measurable gains in biodiversity through conservation or restoration (Ducros and Steele, 2022). There are two main types: active restoration and conservation of threatened biodiversity (avoidable biodiversity loss). Credits are considered as having great potential to mobilise private conservation finance (Nature Finance, 2023).

A recent review of 34 pilot projects of biodiversity credits analysed the potential opportunities and barriers (Wunder et al., 2024). The review emphasizes on how new monitoring techniques are needed to help quantify biodiversity and calls for robust crediting baselines, standards, governance, and impact evaluation. The UK adopted the integration of “biodiversity net gain” policy (DEFRA, 2025), which ensures that developers must deliver a net gain of 10%. This is measured through biodiversity units, which are estimated based on size, quality, location and type of ecosystem. Hence, the units lost through a new development are estimated to calculate how much should be restored, to which the 10% extra must be added. However, purchasing biodiversity credits is not mandatory if the developer is able to provide biodiversity gain on-site or through a mixture of on-site and off-site measures.

3.1.12 Territorial branding

A common way of conservation of local biodiversity and ecosystems is through territorial branding. It involves marketing products or the aesthetic quality of a region based on its natural attributes with the aim of making it more attractive for eco-tourism and local producers, thus creating economic incentives for conservation. The commitment of the region to protect their ecosystems would become part of their identity, increasing the value of local goods, tourism and other investments (Albaladejo-Garcia et al., 2024). For example, the Sierra Espuña Regional Park in Spain, utilized this approach for local honey. Consumers were willing to pay around 30% more for honey carrying the sustainability brand of the park than for conventional honey. These premiums reflect the value people place on supporting ecosystem services and biodiversity.

3.1.13 Swap schemes

Swap schemes aim to compensate landowners who lost land due to conservation policies by granting them access to other productive land, providing a mechanism to reconcile conservation with the livelihood of the local community. In these schemes, the individuals who give up the land for conservation receive an equivalent access to alternative plots or to a share of collective agricultural yields. A limitation with this approach is that it relies on the availability of publicly managed land, as long as strong governance to manage land rights and distribution. An illustrative example of swap schemes can be found in Staccione et al., (2021), where the researchers propose a swap scheme for retention ponds in agricultural land in the North of Italy.

In the following subsection, as part of the outcomes of one of Naturance innovation labs, we use expert elicitation to explore their effectiveness and potential for mainstreaming investment in NBS. This is particularly insightful since evidence remains scarce and often focuses on individual case studies. We also delve into their main strengths and potential limitations in practice.

3.2 Lessons learnt from Innovation Lab

These instruments were discussed with industry and academic experts during Innovation Lab (IL) workshops. Specifically, the IL led by KIT, explored investment opportunities in nature conservation within the EU's protected area network, with the aim of stimulating and scaling up private investment. The IL builds on the urgent need for mechanisms to attract private capital alongside public support, given the large financing gap for conservation and the increasing pressures of climate change. The IL brought together researchers, experts, and businesses to evaluate promising financial instruments and assess barriers. Building on these insights and concrete case studies, discussions focused on opportunities to make nature restoration economically viable.

To support this discussion, a survey listing possible financial instruments and approaches for private nature conservation investments was circulated among experts. Respondents were asked to score each instrument on its effectiveness in advancing private investments in nature protection, at both small and large scales (1 = Not Appropriate | 5 = Highly Appropriate), and to provide comments on their strengths and weaknesses in the application to nature conservation and NbS. The results are reported in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Innovation Lab assessment of instruments

Rank	Instruments	Vote	Strengths	Weaknesses
1	Public-private partnership (PPPs)	4.2	Unlock private investment when public funds share risks; enable impactful collaboration.	Require time to build trust; politically sensitive; complex design; unclear division of responsibilities.
2	Insurance schemes	3.9	Many examples exist; crucial for climate risks; can link with land stewardship and agriculture.	Hard to scale and replicate due to strong local context.
3	Green bonds	3.9	Established and familiar financing tool; can be one part of the solutions	Still underused; often limited to paper commitments.
4	Payment for ecosystem services (PES)	3.8	Provide incentives for conservation; can be tied to measurable outcomes.	Difficult to scale; high transaction costs; often seen as a cost rather than an investment.
5	Environmental Impact Bonds (EIBs)	3.7	Build on known bond models; link returns to project performance.	Complex contracts; few tested cases; usually complement, not replace, other tools.
6	Grants	3.4	Widely applied; effective to kick-start initiatives.	Limited scale; constrained public budgets; not sustainable long term without private co-finance.
7	Biodiversity offsets	3.4	Can work if mandatory and well-regulated.	Risk of misuse; only valid as a last-resort measure; can generate perverse incentives.
8	Impact funds	3.4	Can combine financial returns with positive environmental outcomes.	Few concrete examples in Europe; require clear return expectations (not philanthropy).

9	Crowdfunding/community financing	3.3	Engages local communities; already applied in various contexts; scalable in niche settings.	Not widely scaled; uncertain long-term sustainability.
10	ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) metrics	3.2	Increase transparency; useful for portfolio-level assessment.	Do not provide clear direction; effectiveness depends on regulation; insufficient alone..
11	Biodiversity credits	3.2	Engage the private sector; potential to channel new funding.	Immature market; few real cases (especially in Europe); risk of greenwashing and weak standards.
12	Territorial branding	3.1	Strengthens local identity; supports eco-tourism and producers.	Needs strong management and investment; scalability remains limited
13	Swap schemes	2.8	Can provide compensation for land users.	Risk of overexploitation; limited practical use; little tested experience.

Key messages from the IL discussions on survey results highlighted the need for stronger networks and blended finance approaches to align funding opportunities, with PPPs seen as effective in de-risking and legitimising investments, while grants remain useful but insufficient on their own. On the private side, insurance however raised some concerns, as companies tend to react to risks through higher premiums or service withdrawal rather than funding prevention, making collective approaches or PPPs more viable. As well, biodiversity credits could help but risk replicating carbon market flaws, so the focus should be on genuinely “nature-positive” schemes. ESG frameworks, biodiversity offsets, and the EU taxonomy are emerging as strong drivers by linking nature loss directly to compliance, risk management, and stakeholder expectations. Territorial branding and eco-tourism appear undervalued in survey results despite proven importance in practice.

During the IL workshops, experts identified and discussed both barriers and opportunities, as well as the actions needed to support private investment in nature conservation. Main barriers identified include the lack of clear standards and guidelines (creating risks of greenwashing and high compliance costs, especially for SMEs), uncertainty and long lead times in returns, performance risks of NBS, regulatory instability, and the persistence of harmful subsidies. Additional challenges include the small scale of many projects, the difficulty of valuing multiple co-benefits and diverging sectoral perspectives. To address these issues, stakeholders emphasised the importance of transparent standards, robust valuation frameworks and stronger governance to foster trust. Opportunities lie in developing hybrid business models, bundling projects to increase their scale, and creating intermediary structures to manage revenue streams. Complementary income sources, such as eco-labelling, ecotourism and circular economy products, and insurance-backed guarantees can further reduce investment risk. Blending green and grey infrastructure, co-creating scenarios with stakeholders and bridging the gap between scientific and economic perspectives were identified as conditions that would enable incentives to be aligned, risks to be reduced and long-term private

finance to be attracted. Table 3.3 summarises some considerations about how financial instruments can address these barriers and facilitate the required actions.

Table 3.3: Financial instruments overview

Challenges, Needs & Trade-offs	Opportunities, Enabling Conditions & Actions	Instruments & Mechanisms
<p>Lack of standards and guidelines: fear of greenwashing/greenhushing, reputational risks, complexity of frameworks (e.g., CSRD).</p>	<p>Evidence Generation and Valuation: to inform standards, impact measures and metrics; foster trust through robust guidelines and governance.</p> <p>Capacity Building: to support smaller actors with shared approaches.</p> <p>Bridging scientific and economic perspectives: to foster mutual understanding; support the advancement of pragmatic market tools; emphasize multifunctionality and cross-sector benefits to strengthen investment cases.</p>	<p>ESG and Biodiversity Offsets ESG metrics and EU taxonomy drive biodiversity actions to manage real business risks (e.g., supply chains). Biodiversity offsets can help to mitigate supply risks and support compliance but need careful use to avoid loopholes.</p>
<p>Uncertainty and delayed ROI high upfront costs, long lead times, small project scales discourage private investors.</p>	<p>Business Models for NBS: to identify hybrid revenue streams, staged returns, public co-investment to de-risk early phases and incentivize early movers.</p>	<p>PPPs and Grants PPPs help de-risk financially and legitimize investments; grants kickstart projects but require blended models for long-term sustainability.</p>
<p>High performance risks of NBS: difficult to model effectiveness, especially under climate change and extreme events; uncertainty in outcomes.</p>	<p>Insurance Sector Engagement: to develop collective or government-led approaches; insurance-backed guarantees.</p> <p>Intermediary structure: coordinating bodies, funds, or vehicles to pool risks and revenues; to enable policy-driven project bundling and strengthen region-wide strategies.</p> <p>Blending green and grey infrastructure: to scale and align with public authorities; embed NBS in broader infrastructure and adaptation plans to increase feasibility and appeal.</p>	<p>Insurance Schemes Collective, public-led insurance approaches can be viable in the context of proactive risk reduction, especially for public goods.</p>
<p>Regulatory instability: unpredictable policies undermine confidence; demand for long-term clarity.</p>	<p>Policy & Governance Stability: to embed NbS in national adaptation strategies; long-term stable frameworks to support investments.</p>	<p>PPPs Benefit from stable policy environments; increase legitimacy and facilitate mixed stakeholder involvement.</p>

Harmful subsidies & conflicting incentives: agricultural subsidies incentivize damaging practices; high opportunity cost to switch.

Complementary Income Streams: eco-labelled products, ecotourism, circular economy products (e.g., salt marsh honey) to redirect incentives.

Economic drivers of degradation: to realign economic incentives to support ecological recovery and community well-being; promote new ownership and integrated governance models.

Territorial Branding and PES

Territorial branding is underused but has high potential to leverage local markets for complementary streams; PES schemes replace harmful subsidies and encourage restoration investments.

Multiple co-benefits complexity: shared, intertwined benefits make it hard to define single value propositions; risk of conflict or hesitation.

Multi-criteria Valuation & Transparent Benefit Sharing: to create robust valuation frameworks; transparent agreements; co-design to align multiple stakeholder priorities.

Bridging scientific and economic perspectives: to foster mutual understanding; support the advancement of pragmatic market tools; emphasize multifunctionality and cross-sector benefits to strengthen investment cases.

Biodiversity Credits

Can drive “nature-positive” investments but must avoid carbon-market loopholes.

Context-specificity & small scale: many projects are too small; need for tailored approaches; conflict between local legitimacy and large-scale finance.

Capacity Building and Project Bundling: to support smaller actors with shared approaches.

Context-specific policies: tailored opportunities

Bridging scientific and economic perspectives: to foster mutual understanding; support the advancement of pragmatic market tools; emphasize multifunctionality and cross-sector benefits to strengthen investment cases.

PPPs, Community Financing, Impact Funds

PPPs enable aggregation and scaling; community financing ensures local buy-in; impact funds allow regional pooled investment.

Multi-sectoral perspective & stakeholder tensions: different motivations and cycles per sector; local resistance to mainstream business; need for cross-sector synergies.

Co-creating Scenarios: to highlight multiple benefit streams; integrate cultural and social co-benefits; foster trust and legitimacy.

Intermediary structure: coordinating bodies, funds, or vehicles to pool risks and revenues; to enable policy-driven project bundling and strengthen region-wide strategies.

Crowdfunding, Community Finance, PPPs

Crowdfunding builds trust; community finance empowers local actors; PPPs integrate diverse perspectives and legitimize cross-sector collaboration.

Overall, no single financial tool can overcome barriers to scaling NBS. Their effectiveness depends on context, governance stability, and the ability to combine instruments. For example, PPPs, grants, and insurance schemes play central roles in de-risking and legitimising investments, but could be complemented by PES, territorial branding, biodiversity credits, or community financing to secure local buy-in and diversified revenue streams. Additionally, clear standards, robust valuation

methods, and stable policies are essential to build trust and avoid greenwashing. Project bundling and integrating NBS with grey infrastructure can help attract larger-scale investments. A way forward can be, therefore, to cluster instruments according to the barriers they address and combine them into adaptive mixes tailored to specific challenges and sectors, enabling sustainable private investment in nature conservation.

4 Financial instruments in practice: Insights from an Innovation Lab in the UK

To move the focus of current NBS research beyond instruments such as green bonds and biodiversity credits, this Innovation Lab led by LSE explored broader regulatory enablers that can unlock both funding and innovative solutions to enhance natural urban flood risk management. To this end, the LSE team convened a small group of experts to identify key opportunities and challenges to a newly introduced Biodiversity Net Gain legislation. The regulation, which came into effect in England from February 2024, aims to ensure that ‘development has a measurably positive impact (net gain) on biodiversity, compared to what was there before’ (UK Government, 2025). When developers undertake a project, BNG mandates that they must provide a minimum of 10% biodiversity net gain by the end of the development, and the habitat they create or enhance must be maintained for a minimum of 30 years. For LSE’s innovation lab, this presented a particularly compelling business case, given BNG’s potential to enhance urban ecosystems and boost natural resilience against flooding.

Figure 4.1. Biodiversity Net Gain

The innovation lab first aimed to identify key opportunities for NBS arising from BNG, and then to develop insurance-relevant applications around them. Particularly, the Lab looked to go beyond traditional risk transfer and extend its approach to urban flood risk management.

Throughout the Lab, experts from the financial sector (Flood Re, Marsh McLennan, Green Finance Institute) and environmental organisations (Dark Matter Labs/TreesAI, Sniffer) explored the potential of using BNG not only as a regulatory requirement but as a transformative tool for strengthening resilience to flooding. The case studies analysed throughout the workshops allowed the lab participants to map out worked examples and identify focus areas for future research. While

the challenges of implementing BNG in densely populated areas remain substantial, expert discussions highlighted opportunities to create more sustainable, citizen-friendly urban environments.

The Lab identified several priority areas for deeper exploration:

Research & Collaboration

- How can we foster effective interdisciplinary collaboration among urban planners, ecologists, engineers, insurers, financiers, property developers, and policymakers?
- How can we develop comprehensive strategies that address multiple urban challenges simultaneously?

Policy Development

- How can we raise awareness of the opportunities to integrate BNG into broader urban development and flood risk management strategies?
- How can we navigate policy and regulatory barriers - such as zoning laws, building codes, and environmental impact assessments - so they include criteria that promote BNG and flood risk mitigation?

BNG Underwriting Solutions

- Can BNG act as a catalyst for new insurance and financial solutions?

Key Examples and Recommendations

Hull Case Study

Throughout the lab, experts analysed a recent case study of leveraging BNG to strengthen urban flood resilience. Hull and the East Riding of Yorkshire face some of the highest flood risks in the UK - from the coast, rivers, and surface water. In collaboration with the Living with Water Partnership (LWWP), the city recognised a unique opportunity to link BNG with its Blue Green Plan, using it to retrofit sustainable drainage systems (SuDS) and other natural flood management solutions.

For a small city with limited open space, every intervention must deliver multiple benefits - reducing flood risk while improving biodiversity, public amenity, and community wellbeing. By integrating BNG into SuDS design, Hull has shown how biodiversity policy can directly support flood resilience.

This work led to the creation of a BNG/SuDS toolkit which ensures that biodiversity gains are achieved within the city (rather than within the off-site units), where they deliver the greatest social and environmental value. The project demonstrates how BNG can move beyond regulation to become a driver of urban resilience, sustaining nature and ecology within the city.

Key insights:

- External expertise (Atkins) helped identify how small design changes can unlock BNG benefits and attract new funding streams for flood schemes.
- Collaboration between Hull City Council, East Riding of Yorkshire Council, and Yorkshire Water shows the power of cross-sector partnerships in turning policy into practice.
- By aligning funding and planning mechanisms, Hull has laid the groundwork for using BNG to finance and sustain green infrastructure that manages flood risk naturally.
- Despite challenges with funding, capacity, and community engagement, Hull's experience highlights how BNG can act as a practical enabler of nature-based flood solutions, delivering lasting value for both people and the environment.

The Hull case study provided a practical example of how BNG can be used to enhance urban flood risk management. Building on this, the Lab discussions enabled experts to develop key recommendations for the insurance industry and outline how such approaches could serve as blueprints for similar solutions elsewhere.

Key Recommendations for the Insurance Sector:

1. Support efforts to deliver urban nature as part of effective risk reduction strategies, e. g. through co-investing and risk-reduction incentives
2. Collaborate to collect, analyse, and share relevant data, incorporating relevant indicators and metrics
3. De-risk BNG investments:
 - The insurance sector can help ensure the permanence of BNG outcomes by adapting mechanisms from the carbon credit market that address 'reversal risk' - where biodiversity or habitat gains are later lost, undermining long-term impact.
 - The insurance sector plays a key role in helping developers and environmental consultants mitigate potential liabilities arising from BNG projects - whether due to underperformance (for example, incorrect species selection or change in site management) or operational risks such as a shortage of skilled ecologists. Traditional products, including environmental impairment liability and business interruption insurance, alongside emerging parametric solutions managing nature loss risks, can all serve as effective risk transfer mechanisms for BNG (Marsh, 2025)

5 Case study illustration of an assessment of metrics: A societal CBA

In this section, we will showcase the results of a societal CBA that was produced with the improved methods for assessing the risk reduction and co-benefits of NbS introduced in Deliverable 4.2. The CBA serves as a tool to assess the effectiveness and economic efficiency of NBS in reducing climate-related risk, in a way that they can be compared with traditional solutions. The main aim is to demonstrate how improvements in risk modelling, co-benefits assessments and insurance modelling translate into better informed policy and investment decisions. Additionally, we will delve into a holistic analysis that includes and monetizes co-benefits, which would increase the attractiveness of NBS for investors. However, we will also discuss how identifying the beneficiaries can pose additional challenges that would translate to the question of who should be paying for these policies.

A social welfare perspective increases the attractiveness of investing in NBS for climate risk reduction for the public sector. These interventions provide public goods (such as biodiversity improvements and recreation), which justifies our societal scope, rather than solely focusing on how reduced risk makes a case from investment from the insurance sector. These benefits are likely to increase social welfare overall. However, insurers' stake may be limited to how the reduction in risk impacts insurability and insurance uptake through reduced premiums. The societal CBA allows integration of both market and non-market benefits, and it produces a transparent overview of who benefits from the NBS investment, to what extent, and who (should) pay(s) for the investment. For example, there may be a strong case for (local) governments to partially fund NBS investments proportional to the amount of (semi-)public goods generated by such investments. Governments may fund NBS investments by collecting local taxes, which they may charge in a targeted way if NBS benefits are unequally distributed within their jurisdiction. Insurers could potentially also contribute to funding NBS investments, proportional to the reduction in the risk that they cover, and dependent on the type of insurance system in place (see Section 5.6). Section 5.7 reflects on how this societal CBA may be useful to create an investment-case for funding NBS.

5.1 Literature review

Traditional CBAs have been historically used as a tool to inform investment decisions and have become one of the most important tools for performance appraisal. It aims to estimate the benefits and costs of a project over a set time horizon. For a project to be desirable, the benefits should not only exceed the costs, but also provide a better return than the other competing alternatives (OECD, 2018). This can help to simplify decision-making processes and make several alternatives comparable as the outcome figures are presented in the same unit. However, for CBA to be useful, the data available should allow the assessment of all benefits and costs.

Societal CBAs focus is to allocate the resources efficiently from a social perspective (IISD, 2025). The main goal is to quantify social benefits and social costs of public investments, not just financial returns. The main difference lies in its ability to capture public goods, externalities or non-market goods. These goods are usually neglected when we focus exclusively on financial impacts on a private actor as they do not directly impact the return on investment (ROI) from the perspective of

the investor. Societal CBAs analyze the overall impact on societal welfare instead of just direct financial returns, and for a different set of beneficiaries in society. This is particularly relevant for the investment in NBS since they deliver public goods. Only focusing on risk reduction would result in undervaluation of the total economic value or social welfare impact of NBS.

This method has been used recently to assess the financial viability of NBS as a way of reducing climate risk compared to traditional grey solutions. Recent literature, both academic and from policy reports, indicates that well-designed NBS are often more cost-effective when it comes to managing climate risks. A 2024 systematic review of 87 studies found that over 80% of cases showed NBS to be more cost-effective than conventional “grey” engineering for disaster risk reduction (Vicarelli et al. 2024). Other studies have arrived at similar findings (Chelli et al, 2025). A recent analysis of 83 NBS projects in the European Alps estimated an average return on investment of 3:1 (Gonzalez Garcia et al, 2025). Exclusively from a risk-reduction perspective, NBS have particularly been found effective for high frequency and lower impact climate adverse events, whereas the effectiveness for the most impactful and lower frequency cases is less clear (Lallement et al, 2021).

Table 5.1: Summary of CBAs on NBS

Study	Scale	NbS type	Discount rate	Time horizon	Sensitivity testing	Benefits
Narayan et al. (2016)	20+ Caribbean countries	Mangroves and coral reefs	4%	30 year	Different rates (4,6 and 7%)	Only risk reduction
Reguero et al. (2018)	Gulf Coast	Wetland restoration	2%	20 and 40 years	2% and 10% discount rates	Only risk reduction
Biasin et al., (2023)	Turin (Italy)	Urban NBS	3%	20 years	5% discount rate	Biodiversity, recreation, risk reduction, temperature regulation
Johnson and Geisendorf (2019)	Berlin	Sustainable urban drainage systems	3%	50 years	1-5% discount rates	Drainage, groundwater recharge, air quality improvements, habitat creation and carbon sequestration
Vicarelli et al., (2025)	Haiti, India, Uganda	Several NBS for risk reduction	3%	20 years	3%, 7% and 10% rates	Risk reduction, carbon sequestration, biodiversity benefits, soil quality, etc.

The trend is that more recent CBAs appear to account for a wider range of social benefits. However, the full range of benefits is still difficult to capture, particularly since some co-benefits are challenging to monetize. This leads to a lack of consideration for environmental externalities and an incomplete inclusion of the full range of benefits (Chelli et al, 2025). An additional challenge for such CBAs is the variability of performance of NBS over time. New studies that have integrated this element have reached the conclusion that the cost-effectiveness of NBS depends on factors such as the maturing time of the ecosystem and the value of the land where the NBS is being implemented (Vogeslang et al, 2023). A recent World Bank report indicated that, in order to articulate the full value and identify the beneficiaries, CBAs require new improved methods to value costs and benefits of NBS for climate resilience (Van Zanten et al., 2023), which is one of the aims of this deliverable. An additional key guideline is to engage local stakeholders, as this would enhance community buy-in and engagement. Hence, we used the outcome of one of the Innovation Labs (WP2) to improve the methodological design of our choice experiment aimed at capturing and monetizing co-benefits.

5.2 Methodology

5.2.1 Societal Cost-benefit Analysis

The goal of societal CBAs is to include the impacts of a particular investment on societal welfare, including market and non-market benefits. Under this perspective, a project with net social benefit >0 is a potential improvement over the baseline (Heijman, 1998). However, NBS should also outperform traditional grey solutions to become the best alternative.

$$NPV = \sum (\text{Benefit} - \text{Cost}) / (1+r)^t \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 shows how the Net Present Value (NPV) is estimated. The social discount rate (r) reflects the preferences of society for present versus future welfare, and it is used to evaluate the desirability of investments that have impacts across a certain time horizon (t). The social discount rate (SDR) is key in climate change CBAs. It is used to estimate how much today's society should invest in trying to limit impacts of climate change in the future. The reasoning for a higher SDR would be that, with future changes in technology and wealth, future generations may be able to deal more efficiently with the impacts than current generations. Generally, the higher the SDR the lower are future benefits valued today, since long-term effects would appear small compared to near-term impacts, leading to policies that mostly benefit future generations being less attractive in our CBA (Spackman, 2018). The trend nowadays is to use lower SDRs in climate change and nature applications of CBAs, giving more importance to the welfare of future generations (Freeman and Groom, 2016; Arrow et al., 2013).

The CBA will rely on several assumptions. Each of these assumptions impacts the way the economic benefits of NBS are assessed. The time horizon (t) will ultimately impact the NPV, as we add the discounted net benefit of each year. The time horizon of 30 years that we have chosen for this CBA shows the long-term nature of benefits of NBS. If, due to decay of benefits over time, the net benefit becomes negative, a longer time horizon can reduce the overall NPV. Second, the 2% SDR was

adopted following the recommendations for CBA by the Government in the Netherlands (CPB, 2025). In order to address the potential variance in benefits depending on the discount rate, we will also report the NPV using a 1% and a 5% discount rate. The analysis assumes that the effectiveness of NBS increases gradually as ecosystems mature, and that maintenance and monitoring costs remain constant over time. Many co-benefits such as biodiversity recovery and recreational value may increase progressively as ecosystems establish and stabilise. To avoid overestimating early-stage benefits in the quantitative analysis, we assume that, during the first five years of the project, the monetary value of all co-benefits is assumed to be 20% of the total value.

The number of beneficiaries is key to the monetary estimation of the co-benefits of NBS. Two beneficiary groups are considered: a conservative estimate including only residents of flood-prone areas ($\approx 12,000$ people) and a broader one including the entire population of Limburg (≈ 1.2 million people), which is the province where the NBS is implemented in our case study. This has a considerable impact, as we multiply the WTP estimations from the DCE by the number of households that benefit from them.

5.2.2 Dynamic Integrated Flood Insurance Model

We apply the Dynamic Integrated Flood Insurance (DIFI) framework (Hudson et al., 2019; Tesselaar et al., 2023) to assess the feasibility of the proposed investment-case, where insurers fund (a part of) the NBS-investment. This would probably need to be done through a consortium of insurers to avoid free-riding. The DIFI-model allows us to assess the impact of NBS on flood insurance premiums and uptake of coverage by households. For this, the model uses flood risk data under NBS-scenarios derived from the GEB model (see Section 5.3.1). The output from the DIFI model is used to assess the value of NBS investments for insurers through improved insurability (reduced unaffordability of premiums), for policyholders through reduced premiums, and for governments through a reduced insurance coverage gap. Besides quantifying these NBS-benefits, we assess the specific investment-case where the insurance industry funds NBS-investments proportional to the level of flood risk reduction they generate, in return for dividends amounting to reduced loss-ratios if premiums are kept constant. The model allows us to combine such dividends and NBS-investment costs to produce an annual return on NBS-investments, which we can use to estimate the payback period of the investment.

The DIFI-model consists of three modules; a flood risk, an insurance sector, and a consumer behavior module. In the following, we dedicate sub-sections to describe the relevant procedures of each module.

5.2.2.1 Flood risk

The flood risk module in DIFI produces Expected Annual flood Damages (EAD) and the volatility associated with this variable, which are main inputs for estimating flood insurance premiums in the insurance sector module. EAD and its volatility are produced using simulated building-level flood damages obtained from the GEB model, which we aggregate to postcode-level (PC5-level in the Netherlands) as flood insurance premiums are generally not determined on building-level. As the

GEB model application is described in Section 5.3.1, we will not repeat this procedure here. The GEB model produces flood damages for 7 return-periods (1/25, 1/50, 1/100, 1/200, 1/250, 1/500, 1/1000 years), considering three NBS-scenarios (current conditions, improved flood retention ponds, and a combined NBS scenario). For each NBS-scenario, DIFI applies a monte-carlo simulation that randomly draws probability-weighted flood impacts per building. Estimating the average and standard deviation of these randomly drawn values respectively gives the EAD and its volatility.

5.2.2.2 Insurance sector

The insurance sector module in DIFI produces insurance spatially explicit premiums for several stylized insurance systems and premium-setting rules. For this study, we produce premiums for three of such stylized systems, each of which has different (dis)advantages and opportunities in terms of (co-)investing in NBS. The three flood insurance systems we classify are fully private with risk-based premiums, fully public with flat-rate premiums, and a public-private partnership (PPP) with partially risk-based premiums. These stylized insurance systems represent certain fundamental differences in risk-allocation between households, insurers, and governments, that are observed in practice. We formally describe the premium-setting procedure for the risk-based private flood insurance system and provide intuitive descriptions of the premium-setting rules for the other systems. We refer to the original publication of the DIFI-model (Hudson et al., 2019) for formal documentation of premium-setting procedures for all stylized insurance systems.

Flood insurance is an attractive product for many property-owners as it transfers the potentially disastrous impact of a flood from them to an insurer, for which the insurer charges a more manageable annual premium. Insurers are able to carry risks of individual property-owners by pooling them together such that on average indemnity payouts are equal or less than income through premiums (and for many insurers also investment-returns). Insurers have a choice concerning how they price insurance coverage, particularly concerning the extent that they spread risk amongst policyholders and between different insurance products. As this study is focused on flood risk, we ignore the risk-pooling process of multiple types of risks. Insurers may, for example, charge higher rates to policyholders that are located in high-risk zones than to those in safer regions. In a competitive insurance market, and if regulation allows it, premiums tend to become reflective of the risk of individual policyholders. The accuracy of estimating such risk-based premiums is one of the main ways in which an insurer may outcompete rivals, as it is able to attract relatively low-risk policyholders while leaving competitors with policyholders with relatively high-risk policyholders for whom these insurers charge insufficiently high premiums. Concerning flood insurance, we see no evidence yet of building-level risk-based premiums being charged anywhere, which is largely due to insufficiently detailed risk assessment tools being used by insurers. Although the GEB model allows a building-level assessment of flood risk, for the insurance application we apply postcode-level flood impact data, as this is more reflective of how risk-based insurance is applied in practice.

The estimation of the risk-based flood insurance premium charged by a private insurer is depicted in the following equation:

$$\underline{\pi}_{j,t} = (1 + \lambda) \left(E \left(\underline{L}_{j,t}(p) - \underline{D}_{j,t}(p) \right) + r * \sigma \right) + (1 + \lambda) \left(E \left(\underline{L}_{j,t}^{RR}(p) - \underline{D}_{j,t}^{RR}(p) \right) + r * \sigma^{RR} \right) \quad (2)$$

The final premium charged to a policyholder $\underline{\pi}_{j,t}$ is determined on geographical scale j , which is postcode-level, and at time t , both current conditions (2025) and under climate change for the end of the century. Moreover, the premium is estimated separately for the different NBS-scenarios. The premium is made up of two segments, where the first segment represents coverage and premium-setting by the insurer, and the second segment (where variables are denoted with the superscript RR) represents coverage and premium-setting by the reinsurer. In this stylized representation, the insurer transfers 15% of the flood risk it carries to a reinsurer in a stop-loss type of contract. The insurer covers expected losses L subtracted by the deductible D , which equals 15% of damages when a flood occurs. For losses L , the insurer considers the EAD estimated in the flood risk module of DIFI. On top of the premium that represents EAD, the insurer charges a premium based on the volatility of risk ($r * \sigma$), where a risk aversion factor is multiplied with the standard deviation associated with EAD. This risk-aversion factor is set at 0.5%, based on Hudson et al. (2019). Finally, lambda represents the loading factor charged on top of the risk premium, which for insurers includes only cost-loading of 20%, while reinsurers charge a 50% loading factor that also captures profit-loading.

Flat-rate premiums, charged in a public flood insurance system, are estimated in DIFI by dividing the region's aggregated EAD over the amount of households, subtracted by a 15% deductible for each policyholder. Although flat-rate taxes are often applied nationally (e.g., France, Belgium, Spain), here we estimate what this premium would be if we only consider the Geul catchment. As this insurance is provided by the government, which may be considered risk-neutral, there is no additional premium for the volatility of risk carried by the public insurer. Additionally, the premium in this system may be charged together with homeowner taxes, making the cost-loading factor negligible.

Finally, we estimate a limited risk-based premium, charged under a PPP between insurers and the government. This type of premium is based on how flood premiums are set in the UK's Flood Re, which is a public-private reinsurance pool that includes the government and all insurers that provide flood coverage in the UK. With the aim to keep flood premiums affordable in high-risk areas, this system maintains a premium-cap, where the risk-premium that exceeds this cap for high-risk policyholders is shared equally through the reinsurance pool amongst policyholders that remain below this cap. Through limited-risk based premiums, this insurance system aims to balance advantages of both private systems (e.g., providing financial incentives for risk-conscious decision-making by policyholders) and public systems (e.g., preserving solidarity between high- and low-risk households). In our assessment of the PPP-premium, we maintain a premium cap of €720, which is roughly 2% of median income in the Netherlands. As in the UK's Flood Re system, we estimate the cumulative risk-premium that exceeds the cap and spread this equally amongst households in the Geul-catchment that pay less than the cap.

5.2.2.3 Consumer behavior

In the Netherlands, Germany, and many other countries, flood insurance coverage is optional for homeowners. The consumer behavior module of the DIFI-model allows us to estimate the demand for flood coverage by households that are exposed to floods, and the impact that flood risk-reduction through NBS may have on this demand. A projection of insurance uptake by homeowners allows us to estimate the flood insurance protection gap, which is an important estimate for flood risk managers, for example in order to budget potential ad hoc public flood compensation. The assessment of insurance uptake is not relevant for the stylized public and PPP flood insurance arrangements, both of which maintain insurance uptake requirements.

The consumer behavior module of the DIFI-model applies a subjective expected utility (SEU) decision-framework for each simulated household, which in this study includes all households exposed to floods in the Geul-catchment. For each exposed household, if the premium is affordable, its SEU of purchasing insurance is compared to its SEU of not purchasing insurance coverage. Affordability is assessed by considering whether paying the premium does not cause a household's poverty adjusted disposable income to fall below the poverty line. A household's income is determined by taking a random draw of a log-normal distribution of Dutch income. Poverty-adjusted income considers how much of this income is left after paying fixed expenses, which is assessed by subtracting 60% of median income from this random draw of income. If the premium is larger than poverty-adjusted disposable income, insurance coverage is considered unaffordable and the household will not be insured. For households that can afford the premium, SEU of buying flood insurance is given by:

$$SEU(\text{insurance})_{i,s} = \beta_i p U(W_i - \gamma_i D(L_{i,s}) - \pi_{i,s}) + \beta_i (1 - p) U(W_i - \pi_{i,s})$$

which sums the expected utility of a flood occurring with probability p in a given year and the expected utility of a flood not occurring. If a flood occurs, the household's wealth (W) is reduced by the deductible (D) and the premium (π). The subscript i indicates that the variable varies per assessed household, whereas s indicates that it varies per NBS-scenario. Wealth is determined by multiplying the household's income (drawn randomly from a log-normal distribution) with a fixed wealth-to-income ratio, which is approximately 3 for the Netherlands. The deductible is 15% of flood losses (L) that occur with the considered flood probability, which is determined by applying the flood probability in the fitted flood probability-impact curve established in the flood risk module of the DIFI-model. The estimation of the premium is described in the previous sub-section of this report, and is run separately for risk-based premiums on postcode- and building-level. We apply a logarithmic utility function, which is an established method for simulating risk-averse decision-making. We apply subjective parameters β and γ which represent flood probability and impact misperception. These parameters are drawn randomly from normal distributions calibrated based on survey data from Mol et al. (2020).

The SEU of not buying insurance is given by:

$$SEU(\text{no insurance})_{i,s} = \beta_i p U(W_i - \gamma_i L_{i,s}) + \beta_i (1 - p) U(W_i)$$

where the main differences are that with flood probability p a household faces expected flood losses L , and that with the probability of no flood occurring a household can maintain its wealth fully.

5.3 Data collection

5.3.1 Flood-risk modelling

For this study the novel coupled model GEB (Geographical, Environmental, and Behavioral) is developed, which is described in detail in Bril et al. (forthcoming). The model couples a hydrological model, a hydrodynamic model and a flood risk model to calculate the flood risk reducing effect of several adaptation measures. The simulation procedure assesses flood risk as a product of three components; hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, which is an established approach for natural catastrophe risk modeling. In the following, we describe how each of these components is applied in the GEB model, and how flood risk reduction resulting from the defined NBS-scenarios is assessed. Figure 5.1 presents an overview of the modeling setup applied for this research.

Figure 5.1: Schematic overview of the developed flood risk assessment procedure within the GEB model.

In Figure 5.1 we can see that the flood hazard module (5.3.1.1) uses a submodel (SFINCS) to simulate flood inundation, which applies probabilistic meteorological data, static geographic data and data on soil properties related to infiltration. SFINCS is an established flood hazard model that combines both hydrologic and hydrodynamic processes. This research studies the effectiveness of several NBS-strategies to reduce flood risk in the Geul catchment. Assessed NBS-measures, which affect the static geographic input data applied in SFINCS, are presented in 5.3.1.3. The output of the flood hazard module are maps of flood extents associated with different probabilistic events (return

periods). These maps of flood extents are applied in an exposure and vulnerability module (5.3.1.2) to estimate flood risk. The projection of flood exposure is done on building-level using data from OpenStreetMap (OSM). Additionally, the ESA landcover map is used to project exposure of land-use classifications not used in OSM. The flood vulnerability of exposed assets is represented by stage-damage curves (also known as depth-damage curves) designed based on a dedicated survey done for this in the case study area. Model output (5.3.1.4) includes the monetary value of flood risk reduction resulting from the assessed NBS-scenarios. Each of the model components developed for this research is described in more detail below.

5.3.1.1 Flood Hazard

SFINCS is a coupled hydrologic-hydrodynamic model with reduced complexity, allowing rapid simulations (Leijnse et al., 2021). The model applies simplified Saint-Venant equations to represent the mass and momentum of overland flow and river discharge. SFINCS has been applied and tested to simulate flooding of various types (Leijnse et al., 2021; Parodi et al., 2020; Röbbke et al., 2021). Although SFINCS can be flexibly applied using various types of forcing data, for this research solely precipitation data is used to force the simulation, as the Geul does not receive inflow from other river systems.

The precipitation data used in the hazard module consists of national extreme value rainfall statistics (obtained from STOWA, see Nicolai et al., 2024) associated with seven return periods between 25 and 1000 years. It is assumed that these rainfall events occur evenly over the Geul-catchment, which is simulated at a spatial resolution of 5 meters. The model setup is validated using rainfall data from the July 2021 flood in the Geul catchment. To do this, we force the SFINCS model using precipitation data associated with the flood event, ranging from 01-07-2021 until 16-07-2021, which we obtain from the ERA5-Land dataset. At the height of this period, the accumulation of rainfall amounted to 96 mm over 48 hours, an event that is expected to occur in this region once every 50 years.

The static geographic input data applied to simulate hydrologic and hydrodynamic processes in SFINCS consists of land-use data derived from the ESA Worldcover 2021 map (Zanaga et al., 2022), which presents a wide range of land cover at 10m spatial resolution. This part of the simulation is where important changes in the system take place due to the implementation of NBS, as the main effectiveness of NbS on reducing flood risk is a result of natural landscape features that stop or reduce the speed of runoff. The effect of different types of land cover on the speed of runoff and accumulation of river discharge is assessed by differentiating the Manning's roughness indicator for these various types of land cover, which are derived from Deltares (2024). Aside from increasing the roughness of the terrain, NBS increases the capacity for infiltration of rainwater. This process is captured by adding additional input files describing soil properties important for infiltration: the maximum soil moisture capacity (which depends on the type of soil), the soil moisture capacity at the start of a rainfall event (which depends on recent meteorological conditions), and the saturated hydraulic conductivity (Deltares et al., 2024). We calculate these inputs with the hydrological submodule of the GEB model (Bril et al., forthcoming).

5.3.1.2 Exposure and vulnerability

Flood exposure is assessed using an object-based approach based on spatial data from OpenStreetMap (OSM). OSM is used to assess the extent to which individual buildings, roads, and railways are located in zones expected to be inundated with a certain probability. OSM is reported to present more than 80% of the built-environment, and include information on the function of the building (e.g., whether a residential or commercial building) (Herfort et al., 2023). OSM has recently become a widely used and well-established method of projecting flood exposure (Koks et al., 2019; Bubeck et al., 2019; Sieg & Thielen, 2022).

We apply stage-damage curves to assess flood damages caused by inundation to exposed objects. The stage-damage curves are separated for various structure and land-use classifications. For the structure and content of buildings, our stage-damage curves are derived from empirical data that was collected after the 2021 flood in the case-study area by Endendijk et al. (2023).

5.3.1.3 Nature-based Solutions

The flood risk assessment developed for this study considers two types of NBS, which are flood retention ponds and reforestation. Here, we describe how these NBS are integrated in the flood risk assessment. In Section 5.4.1 we describe the NBS-scenarios that are used in the CBA, some of which include a combination of different NBS.

Retention ponds

Retention ponds are dedicated areas that are flooded in the case of peak discharge, which aims to reduce the amount of runoff downstream during such events. As there are currently 151 retention ponds in the Dutch section of the Geul catchment, we assess a scenario where 37 additional retention ponds are created in the Belgian and German sections of the catchment, but also where the currently existing retention ponds are deepened by 1 meter. This NBS is integrated in the model by assigning a certain water storage capacity per spatial cell, and by only allowing downstream cells to flood once the storage capacity in upstream cells are full.

Reforestation

Forests have several properties that reduce flood risk compared to many other types of land-uses. Firstly, forested land has a higher water storage capacity within the soil, as the porosity of the soil is higher. Secondly, the saturated conductivity (i.e., the infiltration rate) is higher, meaning that water infiltrates faster into the ground. Thirdly, the overland flow velocity is slower due to more obstructions. The infiltration rate and saturated conductivity of reforestation is modeled by implementing newly developed soil property maps in the geographic input data of SFINCS. The increased overland flow resistance due to reforestation is simulated by changing certain areas used for agriculture with forests in the land-use map and changing the Manning's coefficient accordingly to reflect the higher flow resistance of forests. In the designed reforestation scenario, we implement reforestation exclusively on relatively steep hillsides that are currently used for agriculture. This is

because such hillsides are less suitable for agriculture and, therefore, have lower opportunity costs, and because the potential effectiveness at reducing water flow velocity is higher on hillsides. Finally, in our assessment we assume that the planted forest is 100 years old, thereby discounting an initial period of forest growth during which flood risk reduction may be lower than assessed here.

5.3.1.4. NBS scenarios applied in the CBA

In this CBA, we consider three main policy scenarios to illustrate the impact of NBS on societal welfare. These scenarios are in line with the flood modelling results.

- **Baseline scenario:** The baseline scenario assumes no NBS will be implemented along the Geul catchment. This would require no change from agricultural land to NBS. As a result, the co-benefits from the different NBS estimated in the DCE will be set to zero.
- **Additional retention ponds:** This scenario involves 6 hectares of water storage ponds to be developed in current agricultural land, as well as deepening of the current existing ones. Hence, this would have to effect in opposite directions in terms of economic value. On the one hand, the new NBS reduces risk and provides co-benefits. However, the loss of agricultural land reduces the value for respondents and the purchase cost of the land should also be considered. The costs will include the value per hectare of purchasing agricultural land added to the costs of developing the NBS and maintenance costs. The maintenance costs of storage ponds are assumed to be zero. In this scenario, the increase in co-benefits will be of one level for biodiversity improvements (one extra species in favourable condition), and no recreation is assumed to be available in water storage ponds.
- **NBS scenario with reforestation:** This scenario relies heavily on reforestation. Compared to the previous scenario, an additional 1,000 hectares of previous agricultural land would be used for reforestation. In contrast with the previous scenario, reforestation is assumed to have yearly maintenance costs that will be added to the calculation of the NPV. In this scenario, the co-benefits are assumed to further increase, whereas we assume that recreation options are available in the new forest area.

In the next section, we show the outcomes of these NBS scenarios in terms of flood risk reduction. After this, we describe how co-benefits of these NBS scenarios are assessed, as well as the costs associated with implementing the measures. Additionally, we show how the valuations differ depending on who we consider to benefit from the co-benefits of NBS. In all NBS scenarios, we assume that, during the first 5 years, only 20% of the total economic value of NBS co-benefits is achieved in the reforestation scenario.

5.3.1.5 Flood risk outcomes

The flood risk assessment procedure described above produces building-level flood damages associated with several return periods (flood probabilities). Figure 5.2 presents these results aggregated for the whole Geul catchment. We can see that for any given flood return period,

damages are lower when NBS-scenarios are implemented, compared to the current (baseline) conditions. Whereas the increased capacity of waterbuffers (retention ponds) slightly reduces flood damages, implementation of the NBS scenario with reforestation considerably reduces damages (on average over all return periods by 37% when comparing the high-end scenario to the baseline).

Figure 5.2: Riverine flood damages per flood return-period for the baseline and additional NBS scenarios

Although estimations of flood damages are insightful, particularly for designing flood protection standards or seeking estimates of particular (extreme) events, annualized flood risk estimates are often more useful for flood risk management and insurance applications. Section 5.2 described the process of assessing Expected Annual Damages (EAD) based on flood damage estimates. Figure 5.3 and Table 5.2 present the aggregated and spatially explicit estimates of EAD. In Figure 5.3 we can see that EAD generally becomes higher under baseline conditions for downstream regions in the Geul catchment (closer to where the Geul intersects with the Meuse river, north of Maastricht), which is largely because more discharge accumulates downstream during intense rainfall events. These downstream regions, therefore, also benefit more in terms of flood risk reduction from upstream implementation of NBS. This mismatch in where investments are made and where benefits accrue complicates the financing of NBS, even more so in an international catchment such as the Geul.

Figure 5.3: Expected annual flood damages (EAD) in €(2020) on postcode-level under baseline conditions

Table 5.2 presents aggregate values of EAD under the various assessed NBS-scenarios. Besides overall EAD for the whole catchment (sum), the figure presents percentiles of postcode-regions. We can see that the 75th percentile in terms of flood risk is 0, meaning most postcode regions in the catchment actually do not face any flood risk. Flood risk rapidly increases for higher percentiles. Similar to Figure 5.3, we can see that projections of NBS-scenarios are effective at reducing flood risk, more so for NBS scenario. In brackets we show projections of future flood risk, which is simulated by increasing the return periods associated with the estimated flood damages by a factor 10 (i.e., a current 100-year flood will occur every 10 years under climate change). Projected flood risk under climate change increases overall, but more substantially for the areas already facing relatively severe flood risk.

Table 5.2: EAD under the different NBS-scenarios. Values in brackets show a future projection under climate change.

Statistic	Baseline	Additional waterbuffers	NBS scenario
Sum	€9.8mln (€30mln)	€9.1mln (€25mln)	€5.2mln (€25mln)
90%	€0 (€475)	€0 (€578)	€ (€386)
95%	€14.000 (€16.000)	€14.000 (€16.300)	€7.000 (€18.540)
99%	€465.000 (€478.000)	€373.000 (€504.000)	€152.000 (€571.000)

5.3.2 NBS co-benefits: Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE)

DCEs have been increasingly applied to monetize non-market benefits to inform CBA. The data for the DCE that we used to monetize the co-benefits of NBS for the societal cost-benefit analysis, was collected through a survey in December 2024. The DCE was specifically designed to value different benefits of NBS for flood-risk reduction in the Netherlands. The survey was distributed among nearly 2,000 Dutch citizens, with deliberate oversampling in Limburg—the region most severely affected by the 2021 floods—to ensure that perspectives from a high-risk area were represented. Respondents were presented with six choice cards that contained two NBS policy options and one opt-out (or business as usual) alternative. As it can be observed in the choice card, the options were described in terms of measurable attributes including: type of NBS, biodiversity gains, additional warning, required agricultural land conversion and annual cost.

Table 5.3: Example of a choice card of the Choice Experiment

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Measure	Reforestation	Storage pond	No additional NBS
Required agricultural land	100 hectares	200 hectares	No conversion of agricultural land
Recreation	Water-related activities	Non-water related activities	No additional recreational activities
Biodiversity	4 species reach a favorable status	2 species reach a favorable status	0 species have their status changed to a favorable status
Warning time	1 hour additional time	Half an hour additional time	No additional warning time
Annual increase water tax	200 euro	25 euro	No additional tax
Which would you choose?	●	●	●

This method allows for monetization through the estimation of the willingness-to-pay (WTP) of individual households for NBS. For this illustration, we will employ an attribute-only multinomial logistic model. Unlike multinomial logit models, the mixed logit relaxes the independence of irrelevant alternatives assumption (IIA) and captures preference heterogeneity. This was especially important for attributes like biodiversity improvements or warning time, where respondents may differ strongly in the value they assign. The inclusion of an explicit cost attribute—in the form of higher waterboard taxes—allowed monetary valuation of these non-market benefits by expressing them in consistent euro amounts per household per year. The WTP estimates derived from our

econometric model will be incorporated in the social CBA framework. These will complement the risk reduction estimates. Based on our different scenarios and the affected population, we will estimate the economic value of the co-benefits of NBS.

5.3.3 Cost data

For each of the NBS scenarios, we consider both the capital expenditures of NBS, such as planning or construction work, as well as the operating expenses, such as monitoring and maintenance over time, to sustain the services provided by the NBS over time. The cost data for the different scenarios of NBS implementation have been collected from official sources (Limburg waterboard, Municipality Vught) published by different public entities in the Netherlands. This is a close approximation based on data from existing projects (or official estimations), since the different policies have not been applied already, and there is no primary data. Some of the estimates have been adjusted to inflation, as it can be observed in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Summary of costs of NBS in Limburg

Measure	Construction cost	Maintenance cost	Year / currency	Source	Adjusted costs (2024 EUR)
Retention ponds	€200,000 / new pond	-	€ 2019	Waterboard Limburg (2019, 2020)	€ 245,500/ new pond
	€5,000 / expanded pond				€ 6,137/ expanded pond
Reforestation	€13,750 / ha	€158.48 / ha / year	€ 2020	(Teeuwen et al., 2020) (N en L, 2024)	€ 16,666 / ha
			€ 2024		
Grassland	€10,532 / ha	€326.50 / ha / year	€ 2023	Municipality Vught, 2023) (N en L, 2024)	€ 10,885 / ha
			€ 2024		

Additionally, a comprehensive CBA should also take into account the transaction and opportunity costs, by considering the output of the current economic use of the land and its ownership. We consulted the agricultural land market quarterly report of the Netherlands to retrieve the land acquisition costs. The latest figures were estimated at €91,300 per hectare (Kadaster, 2025). Hence, we use this as the price the government, or a private investor, would have to pay for the land where the NBS would be implemented. Further analysis should also attempt to monetize potential disbenefits or negative externalities from the different NBS interventions.

5.4 CBA setup and assumptions

The results of the CBA are provided below. For each of the three scenarios, we performed a cost-benefit assessment by calculating the present value of the net benefits (NPV) using a 2% discount rate and a 30 year horizon since project implementation. For sensitivity testing, we also applied a 1% and a 5% discount rate. A positive NPV would indicate that the project benefits exceed its costs and that the project is preferred to the baseline (no intervention). We provide the results of the BCR when we only consider the expected annual losses reduction separately and then with all the co-benefits included. However, whereas the wider-society benefits increase social welfare, there is no traditional return on investment. Through the CBA, we'll estimate the point where the investment breaks even (NPV>0) and the total benefits through 30 years.

The key question when including the co-benefits in the CBA is how many people we assume will benefit from the co-benefits. In reality, each co-benefits would require their own individual assessment on beneficiaries since some could be more localized whereas others may benefit people outside the region of Limburg. To show how sensitive the results are to the beneficiaries assessment, we will work with two different numbers of beneficiaries: people living by the Geul catchment (12.000) or the population in the whole province (1.2 million). The valuations of the DCE are derived from an attribute-only Multinomial Logit (MNL) model (Table 5.5), and the resulting estimates are € per household per year. Then, we multiply the WTP in each scenario by the beneficiaries in each case.

Table 5.5: Discrete Choice Experiment MNL modelling results

Variable	Estimate	s.e.	z-value	Significance
Natural Grassland	0.053	0.037	1.42	
Forest	0.297	0.036	8.14	***
Retention Ponds	0.261	0.037	7.07	***
Land Use (per ha)	-0.00018	0.000062	-2.87	**
Recreation (Non-water related)	0.127	0.028	4.46	***
Recreation (Water related)	0.061	0.028	2.14	*
Biodiversity (per species)	0.094	0.005	18.09	***
Warning Time (hours)	0.128	0.016	7.9	***
Cost (€/year)	-0.0044	0.00016	-27.04	***
Alternative-Specific Constant (Status Quo)	-0.526	0.058	-9.05	***

The WTP is estimated as a ratio of the attribute coefficient and the cost coefficient. A positive coefficient in our regression signifies that respondents associate it with a higher utility. On the contrary, a negative coefficient indicates a dislike for the attribute. For instance, the negative coefficient for the "Cost" attribute indicates that respondents respond negatively to an increase in cost holding all else constant, as we would expect. In order to monetize the co-benefits we divide each of the coefficients by the cost attribute. The reasoning is the following: the WTP indicates how

much of an increase in cost the average respondent would accept for an increase in a certain attribute so that their utility remains constant. For instance, to estimate the WTP for an additional hour of warning time (0.128), we divide this coefficient by the cost coefficient (-0.0044). This will reveal how much a respondent is willing to pay per year for an additional hour of warning time (28€ per hour per year). For the CBA application, we will then multiply this value by the number of affected households in each scenario.

5.5 CBA results

In this section, we will discuss the results under conservative scenarios first, considering the defined NBS scenarios, and we will continue by illustrating how these may change if we assume a maximum increase in the co-benefits. In the reforestation scenarios, we assume that, during the first 5 years, only 20% of the total economic value of NBS co-benefits is perceived. In contrast, since retention ponds do not require a first phase of growth like reforestation policies, we assume that 100% of the co-benefits are perceived from the beginning. In Section 5.5.1 we will also delve into the robustness checks to show how the different assumptions about discount rates can potentially change our results and takeaways.

Figure 5.4: Contribution to NPV of different components (2% SDR, NBS scenario)

One of the main takeaways is how relevant the addition of the co-benefits is when it comes to the financial viability of NBS projects. Figure 5.4 shows how the valuation of the different scenarios would differ considerably when the co-benefits are omitted. In the figure, we observe the costs on the left-hand side, and the benefits on the right. First, we look at land acquisition costs, which for the combined NBS scenario is large due to the 1,000 hectares that would be required to purchase for reforestation. Added to this, and next in the chart, we observe the management costs and the setup costs over 30 years. On the benefits side, the largest contributor to the NPV is the risk-

reduction benefits. However, this is not sufficient to break even. The aggregated WTP of co-benefits increases the attractiveness of the investment from a societal perspective., Recreation access in the forest (11 million), increase in the number of species in favourable status (16.5 million), an extra hour of warning time (22.4 million) and the aesthetic appreciation of forested areas (26 million) have a considerable NPV impact in a time horizon of 30 years.

The NPV of the baseline is 0, since there are no costs associated with this scenario and also not risk-reduction benefits. The EAD in the baseline is 8,446,919 EUR. The EAD drops by almost 50% in the combined NBS scenario, which could be seen as the cost of not investing in NBS. Even in the Additional Waterbuffers scenario, with enlarged storage ponds, the co-benefits of NBS make this investment more attractive, as around 75% of the NPV comes from the co-benefits. This is partly due to EAD not reducing by a large margin in this scenario of 6 hectares of storage ponds (7,828,085 EUR). A key challenge of NBS scenarios that require large amounts of land to be converted is the very high cost of purchasing land that is currently being used for agricultural purposes. Whereas the Additional Waterbuffers scenario with water storage ponds requires a very low conversion of agricultural land, the reforestation scenario requires 1,000 hectares that are currently being used for agricultural land to be bought and turned into a NBS. On the one hand, the co-benefits are considerably higher in this scenario, as for instance it allows for recreation. Additionally, the risk reduction impact is considerable, with EAD reducing by almost 50%. On the other hand, purchasing 1,000 hectares is estimated to cost approximately 91 million EUR. This is a very steep investment to break even. Moreover, the negative coefficient associated with land use change in the DCE also indicates potential lack of policy support if this many hectares of agriculture would be lost. This shows that policymakers need to have land use in mind when designing NBS, and try to maximize co-benefits and risk reduction in the most efficient manner. If large-scale NBS are needed, then policymakers can either try to maximize co-benefits or find arrangements besides purchasing the land. For instance, reaching agreements where sustainable agricultural practices can be integrated in the NBS. This would also address food security while improving climate resilience.

5.5.1. Robustness checks

In order to assess whether our results are sensitive to changes in the underlying assumptions, we estimate the NPV of the different NBS scenarios employing different SDR. The choice of the discount rate strongly influences how future benefits - such as risk reduction benefits or recreation - are valued relatively to present costs and benefits. Since NBS generate long-term and intergenerational benefits, applying a higher discount rate shows how conclusions may shift under alternative societal preferences for time and risk. We already consider the lag of certain co-benefits by adjusting the first five years to 20% of the total co-benefits value. This is a critical robustness check and ensures that the policy recommendations remain credible under varying assumptions on how the future is valued. The alternative rates we employ are 1% and 5%. 1% is not a very common SDR, since most social CBAs use SDR in the 2%-4% range (Table 5.1). However, the 2% SDR we employed in the previous section, following Dutch official recommendations, is already at the lower end, making 1% the only viable option. This is still informative, and would show how attractive NBS policies would

be if the preference of presence welfare over future benefits is very low. The 5% SDR is above what is usually used in similar studies and it is commonly used as the upper bound SDR in robustness checks Table 5.1).

NPV for NBS scenarios under different SDR

Figure 5.5: Time series of yearly NPV under different SDR and scenarios

Figure 5.5 Shows that our initial results vary significantly from the retention ponds to the NBS scenario. In 30 years, the NBS scenario has yielded a higher return than the Retention Ponds scenario both at 1% (46 million € to 32 million €) SDR. However, the investment breaks even already in year 5 in the retention pond scenario, whereas this requires more time in the NBS scenario (year 20 at 1%; year 24 at 2% and more than 30 years at 5% SDR). The longer the time horizon under our assumptions, the greater the gap between the benefits in the NBS scenario compared to both the Baseline and the Retention pond scenarios. The higher initial losses are mostly associated with the cost of setting up the NBS and, mainly, purchasing the land. This also explains why the initial negative value is considerably larger in the three NBS scenarios, ultimately leading to a longer period until breaking even. The reason the slope in the curves increases after year 5 is due to the initial lag we assume for co-benefits until year five. Then, the curves flatten at different rates depending on the SDR.

We also showcase how much the valuation would change if we assume that the co-benefits would increase more than one level in the NBS scenario. In this scenario, NBS co-benefits are maximized compared to the baseline, picking the highest available level in the DCE. This is determined by the

highest level of the DCE design. This approach highlights further potential upside of well-designed and effectively implemented NBS. Comparing the results of the previous section to this enhanced co-benefits scenario provides further insight into the range of possible outcomes and underscores the multidimensional value of NbS investments.

Lastly, as an illustration of how the results can change when we assume a higher number of beneficiaries, we estimated the results if we assumed that the beneficiaries from the co-benefits are not only the citizens living alongside the Geul catchment, but all citizens in the Limburg region. Ideally this can be estimated through more sophisticated techniques such as decay functions, but this serves as an illustration. There is a case to be made that recreational benefits may not only benefit people whose house is next to the Geul river and the same case can be made for biodiversity improvements. In this case, the benefited population would increase tenfold, from roughly 16,000 to almost 1.2 million inhabitants (CBS, 2025). Hence, the co-benefits side of the NPV equation is multiplied now by the new population figure. The NPV for the retention pond scenario and the combined NBS scenario is 1,803 million € and 5,883 million € respectively using the conservative estimates at 2% rate. The NBS scenario would also be very high (3,975 million €) even at 5% SDR, whereas it was negative when we considered only the Geul catchment households. These benefits are of course considerably higher, as we are estimating now that almost 68 times the previous population is benefitting from the co-benefits yearly.

5.6 Insurance modelling

The previous sections show that NBS are effective at reducing riverine flood risk and economically viable, which means that some of the beneficiaries of NBS investments are residents or owners of properties that are exposed to floods. Often, properties are insured against flood damages, meaning that insurance policyholders only benefit from risk-reduction through NBS if insurers adjust their premiums accordingly. If insurers do not reduce the premium they charge for coverage proportionally to the level of reduced risk, they will be the main beneficiary of the risk reduction generated by the NBS-investment. If premiums are adjusted accordingly, the reduced premium for policyholders gives a direct monetary benefit of the investment, which governments may seek to collect as a return on their investment. However, this may be complicated, as the premium that is charged by an insurer may be sensitive information that is not publicly accessible. An alternative investment case is for insurers to provide funding for NBS proportional to the level of flood risk reduction it generates. The insurer could then keep premiums constant for a certain amount of years, which would generate a return equal to the level of flood risk reduction of the affected properties it covers. The main attraction of such an arrangement for an insurer are the business values it generates, such as keeping flood risk insurable in high risk areas (i.e., limiting unaffordability of insurance). Important obstacles for this arrangement include competition between insurers and the short-term nature of insurance contracts. In countries where flood insurance is organized privately, market competition and short-term contracts (typically yearly contracts) create the problem that competitors who do not pay for an NBS can underprice coverage in the area benefitting from the NBS. By doing so they may attract more policyholders from the insurer that made the NBS investment and that aims to make a return on this investment. In countries where flood insurance is provided or regulated by a government the investment case of

insurers partially funding NbS based on flood risk reduction is more feasible, as market competition may be limited. As identified in Section 3, public-private partnerships in flood insurance markets may be particularly effective to encourage NBS investments by private insurers.

The following results that are presented and discussed are obtained using the DIFI model (Section 5.2.2), using novel object-based flood projections and NBS scenarios developed for this study (as described in Section 5.3.1). We begin by presenting insurance premiums under the different NBS-scenarios in order to quantify the NBS-benefit of premium-savings. We assess premiums using different stylized insurance systems that have different premium-setting procedures, which represent certain fundamental differences between EU-countries in how flood insurance is organized. These differences in how premiums are set also affect who benefits from the NBS-investment, as will be shown and discussed. We also assess how premiums may be impacted by climate change. After showing the premiums under these different scenarios and arrangements, we show outcomes of the DIFI analysis on insurance uptake. This analysis is only relevant in an insurance system where uptake is voluntary and, usually, provided privately, which means it is less relevant for the assessment of the defined investment-case involving insurers. However, assessing the insurance coverage gap under different NBS scenarios is interesting for public FRM, as improving insurability and reducing the flood insurance protection gap is beneficial from a societal perspective. We end this section with an assessment of the proposed investment-case. More specifically, we assess how much funding could realistically be made available by insurers under the proposed investment-case.

Premiums

The premium that is charged to flood insurance policyholders depends on several important factors, including the degree of risk cross-subsidization. In this analysis we assume that flood coverage is not bundled with other types of risks, meaning the premium only reflects flood risk. In insurance systems where coverage is provided by private insurers, and where regulation allows it, competition amongst insurers generally drives them to charge risk-based premiums. However, the accuracy of available flood risk maps is often a limitation to the spatial level at which premiums can be set. This often means that in insurance systems with risk-based premiums there remains a degree of risk cross-subsidization amongst policyholders within the level of spatial detail. For example, a flood hazard map on a 1x1km-resolution will require risk sharing between policyholders within each 1x1km. Examples of countries where flood premiums are risk-based on a relatively detailed level include the US, the UK, and Australia (OECD, 2016).

Table 5.6 shows summary statistics of risk-based flood insurance premiums. Moreover, it shows premiums considering the flood risk reduction under the defined NBS-scenarios, as well as a projection of flood risk in 2100 considering climate change (in brackets). Average premiums can be seen to decline with more NBS being implemented, from €416 under current conditions, to €364 when additional waterbuffers are implemented, and €274 when the measures under the NBS scenario are implemented. Table 5.6 also shows premiums for the 75th, 95th, and 99th percentiles of the 795 postcode-regions assessed in this analysis. It can be seen that households in most postcodes do not pay a risk-based premium as they are not located in a floodplain. Only at the 95th

percentile of postcode-regions do households pay a premium, which becomes rapidly larger for postcode-regions at the extreme end of flood risk in the Geul-catchment. It can be seen that for households facing high flood risk and premiums in baseline conditions, the effectiveness of the NBS-scenarios at reducing flood premiums becomes higher. In terms of flood risk reduction and saving on insurance premiums, the relatively few postcode-regions at the high end of flood risk in the area are the main beneficiaries of investing in NBS.

Table 5.6: Risk-based flood insurance premiums under the different NBS-scenarios. Values in brackets show a future projection under climate change.

Statistic	Baseline	Retention ponds	Combined NBS scenario
Mean	€416 (€522)	€364 (€418)	€274 (€425)
75%	€0 (€25)	€0 (€27)	€0 (€29)
95%	€41 (€1.330)	€52 (€1.380)	€30 (€1.550)
99%	€1.460 (€15.900)	€1.300 (€13.700)	€670 (€13.200)

Table 5.7 shows flat-rate flood insurance premiums for the Geul-catchment. Such an insurance arrangement essentially spreads flood risk to residential properties (€9.8 mln considering baseline conditions) equally amongst the number of properties (81.822) in the catchment. Flat-rate premiums are usually applied in public or public-private flood insurance systems, where public regulators are able to enforce uptake requirements, which is essential to prevent adverse selection under this arrangement. In practice, flat-rate premiums are usually applied on a country-level (e.g., France, Belgium, Spain), which allows such insurance systems to keep premiums low. Important for our investment-case assessment is that the number of households benefitting from NBS flood risk reduction is high under this insurance system, although the magnitude of the benefit is lower for households exposed to floods.

Table 5.7: Flat-rate flood insurance premiums under the different NBS-scenarios. Values in brackets show a future projection under climate change.

	Baseline	Retention ponds	Combined NBS scenario
premium	€110 (€318)	€100 (€257)	€58 (€258)

The advantage of flat-rate premiums is that insurance does not become extremely costly for some, but remains affordable, particularly when risk is spread over a large geographical area (such as a country). However, flat-rate premiums may be considered unfair to households living outside of floodplains, and it is found to cause moral hazard, a phenomenon where insured individuals no longer make risk-conscious decisions. Households insured against subsidized rates may, for example, be more likely to settle in flood-prone areas (Tesselaar et al., 2023), and they may be less likely to invest in risk-reduction measures (Hudson et al., 2019). To benefit from both types of

insurance systems, a premium cap may be enforced in a risk-based system, where excess risk for high-risk households is transferred to lower-risk households. Such a system is applied by Flood Re in the UK, which is a public-private reinsurance pool that aims to keep flood risk insurable. Besides having influence on premium-setting, a public-private partnership (PPP) of flood insurers and the government may be an effective arrangement to overcome the obstructions to the assessed investment-case caused by competition on the insurance market. Table 5.8 shows what limited risk-based premiums in the Geul-catchment would be if a premium cap of 2% of Dutch median income is maintained. We can see that the most at-risk households pay the capped premium of €720 under all NBS-scenarios, meaning they do not benefit in terms of premium-reductions from the NBS investment. Instead, households with lower risk are more likely to benefit from NBS flood risk reduction, as the total amount of flood risk that these households effectively subsidize is considerably reduced. We can see that under climate change, the mean premium under this insurance system becomes the capped premium, which happens because the excess risk that is cross-subsidized causes the premium for all households to reach the cap. This could already be observed with the flat-rate premium under climate change presented in Table 5.7, which exceeds the cap maintained here. This premium cap is, therefore, not sufficiently high to preserve a financially viable insurance mechanism. Either the cap needs to increase to higher than the flat-rate premium under climate change, or the geographical range of the insurance system should increase (as long as this range includes many low-risk areas).

Table 5.8: Partially risk-based flood insurance premiums under the different NBS-scenarios. A premium cap of 2% of median household income is maintained, where flood risk above this threshold is borne by low-risk households. Values in brackets show a future projection under climate change.

Statistic	Baseline	Retention ponds	Combined NBS scenario
Mean	€100 (€381)	€86 (€300)	€50 (€300)
75%	€82 (€368)	€68 (€225)	€38 (€285)
95%	€124 (€421)	€120 (€338)	€68 (€343)
99%	€720 (€720)	€720 (€720)	€600 (€720)

Using the premiums estimated in Table 5.8, and the investment costs associated with the NBS-scenarios, we can estimate the return-on-investment (ROI) for the defined investment-case. Table 5.9 shows dividends as the aggregate yearly value the insurance industry can generate under the different NBS-scenarios if baseline premiums are kept constant. For example, if the increased waterbuffer scenario is implemented, and insurers do not adjust their premiums accordingly, the flood insurance industry in the Geul catchment may expect average savings on indemnity payments of €975.000 per year. If the insurance industry invests 50% of the implementation costs of this NBS-scenario, its annual ROI is 20%, meaning it is expected to earn back its investment in 5 years. The NBS-scenario has a higher return, but also much higher investment cost, resulting in lower although still substantial ROI. This outcome implies that the proposed investment-case is financially attractive

for the insurance industry. Actions should be targeted at creating suitable conditions for the insurance industry to co-invest in NBS.

Table 5.9: Dividend on NbS-investment for insurer.

	Baseline	Retention ponds	Combined NBS scenario
Yearly dividend	-	€975.000	€5.22mln
Annual ROI*	-	20%	9.5%
Payback period (years)*	-	5	10

*considering an insurer only funds an amount proportional to the flood risk-reduction resulting from the NBS scenario.

Uptake and coverage gap

In the previous section we found that it is financially attractive for the insurance industry to invest in the designed NBS-scenarios. The investment case, where the insurance industry invests in NBS proportional to the flood risk-reduction generated by it, is feasible as long as the needed institutional conditions are in place. For example, government regulation of the flood insurance market needs to restrict the possibilities for policyholders to quit or switch short-term insurance contracts. Only then may insurers invest in NBS that may require multiple years to earn back through savings on indemnity payments.

Currently, in the Netherlands, Germany, and many other countries, such institutional conditions are not in place, as policyholders have the choice each year to quit or switch insurance contracts. Although we advocate the PPP framework for flood insurance, not just for realizing the proposed investment-case, but also for maximizing societal flood coverage, limiting unaffordability of insurance, and providing financial incentives for policyholder-level risk reduction, investing in NBS is still beneficial from a flood risk management perspective. Innovative financial instruments, besides those introduced in Section 3, could help to mainstream financing of NBS. In Table 5.10 we show outcomes of the consumer behavior module of the DIFI-model, which simulates choices and constraints that households face with regards to insurance uptake. We can see that the modeled flood insurance penetration is 40% in the baseline, which is similar to the 25-50% range estimated in EIOPA (2024). We can see that risk-based flood premiums are unaffordable for 13% of households, making unaffordability an important constraint to insurance uptake. The insurance coverage gap in the baseline is €1.78mln, meaning this much uninsured flood damage may be expected on average each year. However, a single flood (e.g., a 100-year flood) will certainly cause substantially more uninsured damages. We can see that the flood insurance penetration rate declines slightly under the NBS-scenario. This means that in the SEU decision-framework that simulates food insurance uptake, coverage is preferred by fewer households as a result of the impact of NbS on (subjective) flood risk. There are more households for whom the reduction in flood risk seems to outweigh the reduction in risk-based premiums as a result of NBS. Despite the reduced

penetration rate, however, the flood insurance coverage gap more than halves with the NBS-scenario, which is a result of the substantial reduction in flood risk.

Reducing the flood insurance coverage gap is an important objective of flood risk managers in many countries (Bellia et al., 2025). Uninsured flood risk creates economic uncertainty after a disaster, as it is often unclear who finances these uninsured damages. Households may have insufficient means to finance reconstruction, meaning the government is often implicitly liable to provide disaster aid. However, the provision of public disaster aid may be slow or insufficient, as governments are usually less efficient in assessing damages and processing payouts compared to insurers (Botzen & van den Bergh, 2008). A delayed reconstruction process is associated with long-term negative macroeconomic impacts (Von Peter et al., 2024). Results presented in Table 5.10 imply that the case for investing in NBS is sensitive to which insurance system is in place. When there is a substantial insurance coverage gap, insurers are less likely to benefit from reduced risk, but it is instead governments and households that benefit directly through lower expected annual damages that need to be considered in budgetary planning. In this case it may be most effective if governments fund NBS-investments, as it is unlikely that households process this information and provide funding accordingly.

Table 5.10: Flood insurance penetration rate under the defined NBS-scenarios for risk-based premiums.

	Baseline	Retention ponds	Combined NBS scenario
Penetration rate	40% (53%)	40% (54%)	36% (54%)
Unaffordability	13% (13.8%)	13% (13.6%)	13% (13.6%)
Coverage gap (uninsured risk)	€1.78mIn (€11.8mIn)	€1.6mIn (€9.3mIn)	€892.000 (€8.7mIn)

Unaffordability is one reason for not purchasing insurance coverage, which we show as a percentage of the population in the Geul-catchment (76.139). Note here that under the maintained poverty criterion there is a baseline poverty rate of 12.9%, meaning that the difference between the unaffordability percentage and the baseline poverty rate is the share of households who will fall into poverty as a result of paying the insurance premium. Finally, the coverage gap shows the amount of residential EAD that is not covered by insurance.

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5.7 Implications for financing schemes

The previous sections show that NbS investments can be beneficial when considering the reduction in riverine flood risk, as well as broader societal values. Accounting for co-benefits appears to be crucial for NBS. These benefits increase considerably in the NBS scenarios. The results are consistent under different SDR and different assumptions of co-benefit improvements. One of the key findings that can limit the implementation and economic feasibility of NBS is the importance of land use change. The CBA results also highlight the importance of adopting a long-term and societal perspective when evaluating NBS, which does not typically align with short-term political incentives or private sector profit-maximizing behaviour. Across scenarios, co-benefits consistently make a difference to make NBS viable, particularly in more ambitious NBS that require large portions of land. Both risk reduction and co-benefits improve in the NBS scenario, but the initial cost is considerably higher. In our case study, it takes approximately 20 years to break even, whereas this occurs only after 5 years in the smaller-scale retention pond scenario. Overall, the high cost of purchasing 1,000 hectares could be the main challenge, which could be an incentive to find alternatives for developing NBS in agricultural land through mixed-use alternatives.

Although the NBS scenarios are beneficial from a societal perspective, it may still be challenging to finance such NBS projects. We assess the feasibility of an investment case where the insurance industry finances the NbS projects proportional to the level of risk reduction generated by it. As highlighted in the Innovation Lab led by KIT (Section 3), this opens the door for PPPs where the public sector collaborates with insurers to develop NBS projects. The insurance industry may then generate returns on NBS investments by (temporarily) keeping premiums constant, while expected damage payouts are reduced. We find that such an investment case is highly attractive, with annual returns on investment around 10% for reforestation and 20% for investing in additional retention pond capacity. However, the attractiveness of this investment case requires the condition that an insurer that invests in NBS does not face the risk that policyholders in the affected region switch to competitors, disabling the insurer from generating a return on its investment. A public-private insurance collaboration, identified as a financial NBS strategy in Section 3.1.1, may be a suitable system to overcome the obstruction to the investment case due to market competitiveness. Although it is unlikely that insurers invest in NBS if market competitiveness is not restricted, the insurance industry may play an important role in facilitating the NBS investment. As described in Section 3.1.2, by adjusting premiums based on NbS flood risk reduction, insurers may aid in expressing NBS benefits in annual monetary values. These values may be used by, for example, governments that consider investing in NBS. Our analysis of insurance premiums shows that, although the benefits of NBS in terms of premium reduction are equal overall for different types of insurance systems, the type of applied premium-setting rule impacts the amount of households that benefit from the NBS investment. For risk-based premiums, the benefits in terms of premium reduction count for fewer individuals than for insurance systems with more risk cross-subsidization. Finally, our analysis of insurance coverage shows clear benefits of NbS investments in terms of a reduced insurance coverage gap. These outcomes may count as direct public benefits, as governments require less funding for ad hoc flood damage compensation.

6 Simulation of adoption of small-scale NbS by insurance consumers (VU)

6.1 Context: The PIISA project

The Piloting Innovative Insurance Solutions for Adaptation (PIISA) project is a Horizon Europe project running from 2023 to 2026. It explores how insurance innovations can contribute to climate change adaptation by incentivising preventive action. PIISA runs in parallel to NATURANCE, with which it shares the overall focus on climate adaptation, but with a specific focus on the role of the insurance sector.

Within this project, one pilot focuses on green roof insurances (Farina et al., forthcoming). Green roofs are a type of small-scale NbS for urban climate adaptation: once upscaled at the city level, they can reduce local pluvial flood risks, improve thermal insulation of buildings, support biodiversity, provide aesthetic and recreational benefits, and protect roof layers against weather damages. Unlike many other NbS, they can be installed on privately owned buildings. Increasing the adoption of green roofs by households is therefore a key condition for scaling up their benefits and co-benefits.

Green roofs have mostly been incentivized through public funding, e.g. through subsidy schemes in some European cities - mainly in the Netherlands and in Germany. Yet insurances have a stake in this. An increase in green roof adoption would lead to reduced pluvial flood risks and damages to buildings, which could lower claims for instance. Yet, it remains unclear how the insurance sector could best incentivize adoption of green roofs. Insurers implementing green roof - or other NbS - products are very scarce.

A nationwide survey was conducted among Dutch households to address this question. The survey included a monetary valuation component, eliciting willingness-to-pay for green roofs, as well as a policy experiment designed to test the relative effectiveness of different incentive schemes. In this experiment, respondents were exposed to scenarios involving municipal subsidies, insurance-based incentives, and non-monetary drivers such as information or descriptive social norms. This approach highlights how households respond to alternative incentive structures. Ultimately this design is a systematic experimental framework that allows to compare and identify the most effective monetary incentives for scaling up green roof adoption.

6.2 A policy experiment on green roofs

The study investigates how different policy incentives influence household intentions to adopt green roofs in the Netherlands. A structured survey was conducted among urban residents, with a sample of 1,660 respondents broadly representative of the Dutch urban population in terms of age and gender.

The central component of the survey is a policy experiment in which respondents are randomly assigned to one of three treatment groups, each corresponding to a different type of financial incentive:

- Municipal subsidies, where a share of installation costs is covered,
- Insurance premium discounts, offering reductions in annual home insurance premiums, and
- Insurance deductible discounts, lowering the deductible payable when making a damage claim.

Within each treatment group, five levels of financial incentives are presented, ranging from no support to full coverage. For each scenario, respondents indicate the probability that they would adopt a green roof. This repeated-measures design enables the estimation of adoption probabilities under alternative policy conditions.

In addition to the treatments, the experiment incorporates measures of psychological drivers based on Protection Motivation Theory (PMT). These include perceived response costs, perceived efficacy of green roofs in reducing climate risks (flooding, heatwaves, and structural damage), and perceived exposure to such risks. Sociodemographic and housing information is also collected to account for heterogeneity in responses.

The data are analysed using a regression analysis suitable for repeated observations per respondent. Each individual provides multiple probability judgments under varying incentive levels, which are modelled using pooled ordinary least squares with cluster-robust standard errors at the individual level. This approach accounts for intra-individual correlation and allows direct estimation of how policy incentives and psychological factors influence stated adoption probabilities. This design provides then a basis for counterfactual simulations that quantify how adoption rates would change under different combinations of policy incentives and behavioural factors.

6.3 Main results, highlights and implications

Figure 6.1: Counterfactual predictions of green roof adoption probabilities under alternative incentive scenarios, showing subsidies, insurance premium discounts, and insurance deductible discounts across incentive levels

The main results of this experiment show that municipal subsidies, insurance premium discounts, and insurance deductible discounts have distinct effects on household intentions to adopt, and that their effectiveness depends on the incentive level. Insurance premium discounts produce the steepest increase in predicted adoption. Uptake rises from approximately 45% to nearly 90% as the discount increases from 0% to 100%, indicating that recurring reductions in annual costs are highly salient to households. Deductible discounts also increase adoption, though more gradually, with a smoother growth curve across levels. By contrast, municipal subsidies exhibit a slower effect at lower levels, but adoption accelerates sharply once subsidies reach 50% or more of installation costs. This suggests the presence of a threshold effect: households are relatively unresponsive to small subsidies but shift behaviour rapidly once installation is perceived as “almost free.”

These differences may be linked to the temporal framing of the incentives. Subsidies reduce the upfront investment but are one-off transfers, while premium and deductible discounts represent ongoing financial benefits, which may feel more tangible at lower levels of support. At higher

subsidy levels, however, the strong uptake response highlights the power of substantially lowering initial barriers to adoption.

Overall, the analysis indicates that insurance-based incentives may be more effective than subsidies at modest levels of support, whereas large subsidies can trigger strong behavioural responses once they cross a perceptual threshold. This finding highlights the potential role of insurers in scaling green roof adoption, while also suggesting that well-designed subsidy schemes remain highly relevant when significant upfront cost reductions are feasible.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable shows how integrating flood-risk modelling, DCEs and insurance modelling can strengthen the case for NBS for flood risk reduction in a societal CBA. Building on the methodological advances conducted in Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2, and based on the feedback received in the Innovation Labs, we assessed two different NBS scenarios for the case study of the European 2021 floods in the region of Limburg. This quantification is also an assessment of the metrics presented in Section 2 (Risk reduction, co-benefits, economic materiality and robustness), particularly those focused on economic soundness and financial viability. Our results highlight that, to make NBS economically feasible, the co-benefits of NBS must be taken into account. The risk reduction benefits of NBS are considerable, with the reforestation (NBS) scenario reducing EAD to half of the original in the baseline. However, the amount of land that has to be purchased to develop these NBS is a key factor when assessing economic feasibility. Additionally, we show that there are already several financing tools that have been used to mainstream investment in NBS. We show how experts in the field view these tools, identifying key benefits and challenges of each instrument. Moreover, the results of Section 5 are aligned with the preference for PPP highlighted in Section 3, since the co-benefits are essential to demonstrate the economic feasibility of NBS. This is further explored through the Hull case study about the BNG policy. Lastly, we explore additional ways of promoting NBS through insurance by showing the effectiveness of premium discounts for green roof adoption.

The DCE shows that respondents are indeed willing to pay for NBS, particularly reforestation policies. Moreover, they also showed a positive WTP for the co-benefits of NBS, revealing potential public support for NBS interventions. On the other hand, some respondents also showed a reduction in utility from agricultural land being converted to NBS. The CBA results show that co-benefits are needed, particularly for the NBS scenario that requires 1,000 hectares of agricultural land to be converted to NBS. The NPV is positive for all SDR except at 5% for the scenario. Smaller scale NBS can be very efficient economically due to low land requirements and considerable reduction in risk compared to the baseline. From a societal welfare perspective, new NBS policies could consider mixed-use of land where some degree of agriculture can still be conducted in the land that also provides risk-reduction services. The DIFI model results complement the CBA by showing that NBS can lower premiums for vulnerable households and reduce the overall protection gap, when premiums are risk-based. Alternative models, such as promoting investment in green roofs through insurance-based incentives, have also been effective in influencing household behaviour. Premium discounts demonstrate strong potential to increase household-level adoption.

These results are also important for the insurance sector. When insurers take NBS into account when estimating flood premiums, insurers may contribute in translating NBS risk reduction benefits into annual monetary benefits for policyholders at risk of flooding. When flood insurance premiums reflect risk of individual policyholders to a high extent, NBS may contribute to keeping premiums affordable for high-risk policyholders. When flood insurance coverage is low, NBS contributes to reducing the flood insurance protection gap, which is uninsured flood risk. This reduces the potential funding required for ad hoc disaster compensation by governments. The previously mentioned benefits of NBS remain largely for policyholders and governments, meaning NBS investments will more likely be funded by these stakeholders than by insurers. In our analysis we also assess an

investment-case where the insurance industry does provide funding towards NBS investments. We show that under an insurance market system that facilitates collaboration amongst insurers and governments (i.e., a public-private-partnership), investing in the defined NBS-scenarios is financially attractive for the insurance industry. The most important enabling condition for this investment-case is that insurers are able to generate a return on their investment in the form of reduced indemnity payouts while keeping premiums (temporarily) constant. In practice this means that insurers need to collaborate on preventing policyholders in the area protected by an NBS-investment from switching to a competing insurer that was not involved in financing the investment. To sum up, both our quantitative results and the discussions with stakeholders in Section 3 show that collaborations between the public sector and the private sector are likely to be needed to mainstream investment in NBS, potentially through PPPs. Policymakers need to consider land-use planning that accounts for the preferences of the local community when designing NBS policies for risk-reduction.

The key recommendations for the scaling up of investment in NBS for the public and private sector are:

- Employ shared metrics and standards to allow for comparability of the effectiveness and desirability of NBS. The metrics proposed in this report allow an assessment on a broad welfare perspective.
- Enable collaborations between the public sector and the private sector in order to collect, analyse, and share relevant data, incorporating relevant indicators and metrics. Alternatively, the public sector can collect open-access data.
- Integrate NBS in spatially detailed catastrophe models that can provide actionable insights into risk reduction, premiums and insurability.
- Assessing flood-risk reduction of NBS requires basin-scale simulations to capture upstream and downstream interactions.
- Stimulating private finance for NBS is dependent on the type of insurance system. In the case of a public-private insurance system, there can be a business case for insurers to invest in NBS for risk reduction.
- Even in the case of a purely public or private system, the assessment of risk-reduction from NBS is still relevant to identify the beneficiaries.
- Complement the risk-reduction estimates with a co-benefits assessment. Monetizing co-benefits in a societal cost-benefit analysis is key to illustrate the economic viability of NBS.
- Account for land-use change as a key component of financial feasibility of NBS. Its financial and social impact should not be neglected by policymakers. Innovative solutions that combine agricultural practices and NBS could increase viability and social acceptance.
- Promote alternative insurance financing mechanisms, such as premium-based incentives for insurance policyholders to adopt NBS.
- Consider private-public partnerships, grants, and insurance schemes as they play central roles in de-risking and legitimising investments, but could be complemented by payment for ecosystem services, territorial branding, biodiversity credits, or community financing to secure local buy-in and diversified revenue streams.

- Implement public policies, such as the Biodiversity Net Gain in the UK, as a potential way for enabling NBS. The insurance sector plays a key role in helping developers and environmental consultants mitigate potential liabilities arising from Biodiversity Net Gain projects.

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